

D3.3 – ImProDiReT Risk Evaluation Approach

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Glossary

Abbreviation /Acronym	Description
ALARP	As Low as Reasonably Practicable
ARDZ	Agency of the regional development of Zakarpattia
CREA	Community-based Risk Evaluation Approach
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessments
DRR	Disaster risk reduction
EU	European Union
EUCPT	European Union Civil Protection Team
GIS	Geographic information system
GIS	Geographical Information System
GPDR	General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679
GSM	Global System for Mobile communication
GSM	GSM Association
HREC	Human Research Ethics Committee
IGS NASU	Institute of Geological Sciences of the National Academy of sciences of Ukraine
ImProDiReT	Improving Disaster Risk Reduction in the Transcarpathian Region, Ukraine
IPs	Implementing Partners
MSFS	Main School of Fire Service
NGO	Non-governmental organization
OCHA	Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
REA	Risk Evaluation Approach
REDA	Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach
SVDDRP	Solotvyno Disaster Risk Reduction Platform
TDRRP	Transcarpathian Disaster Risk Reduction Platform
TUD	Delft University of Technology
UN OCHA	United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

In furtherance of the SENDAI framework, the ImProDiReT project started in March 2018 with a lifetime of 24 months with the financial support of the European Union Civil Protection Mechanism. The project aim is to improve risk governance within the Transcarpathian Communities in Ukraine, with a case study of the Solotvyno village. In the first project year, ImProDiReT has collected risk assessment geodata for the larger Transcarpathia region and Solotvyno municipality in Ukraine. The geodata was collected for a variety of purposes, such as creating models, automatically generating PDF reports, and for integration in web-based applications to evaluate risks and support decision-making. To supplement the geodata, there is need for an evaluation of community perceptions and their level of preparedness and attachment to Solotvyno.

The most challenging phase in the risk management process is risk evaluation. It involves the delineation and justification of judgments on the acceptability and tolerability of certain risks. When a risk is tolerable, additional risk reduction actions need to be undertaken as opposed to acceptable risks where no risk reduction effort is required because the risks are considered to be very low. The difficult task is drawing a line between what is considered 'intolerable,' and 'tolerable' and between 'tolerable' and acceptable.' Current risk approaches rely on two inputs, namely evidence, and values. Renn (2008), explains that values are an essential part of risk evaluation because "what the society is supposed to tolerate or accept can never be derived from looking at the evidence alone" [1], (p. 37)." Hence we have frameworks developed such as the SENDAI framework, which affirm that communities play an essential role in Disaster Risk Reduction decision-making processes [2].

Transcarpathian region is situated in the West of Ukraine. Geographically the region is dominated by the northern part of the Carpathian mountain range, which stretches from Poland and Slovakia in a horse shoe form into Romania, crossing Ukraine. The population of Transcarpathia is multi-ethnic, with several large minority groups, for example Romanians, Hungarians, Russians and Romas. Since the collapse of the Union of the Soviet Socialistic Republics (USSR) the logical connections between Ukrainian institutes and institutions with relevant data on hazards and risk of disasters and the local and regional administration were disturbed. An open, transparent exchange of information has become increasingly difficult at all levels, also in addressing cross cutting issues. The UCPM Advisory mission to the Solotvyno noted this as a major obstacle to come to a good, all-inclusive assessment. In respect to the Sendai framework problems can be seen in the field of understanding risks, risk reduction governance and investing in risk reduction management. D3.3 develops a risk evaluation approach that seeks to address these gaps in Solotvyno municipality, and providing generic guidelines for future DRR projects.

The Building on the previous work done under D3.1 (State of the Art Analysis), and 3.2 (An approach to Identify Local Requirements), D3.3 focused on the development of the risk evaluation approach for Solutvyno municipality. The unique aspects of the Solutvyno case study required a risk evaluation approach that incorporates multiple stakeholders.

Project deliverable 3.3's objective is to develop developing a community-based risk evaluation approach for the Solutvyno Saltmine case study. The Principal Investigator (henceforth "PI") is Prof. Bartel Van de Walle. The risk evaluation researcher is Dr. Abby Muricho Onencan (henceforth "Researcher"), Department of Multi-Actor Systems, Section Policy Analysis, Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management, Delft University of Technology, NL.

The developed household survey seeks to receive input from approximately 1000 to 2000 households. The approach used the outcomes of previous project activities under various WPs as input and requirements for the design and implementation of the risk evaluation approach. The process towards developing the tailored evaluation is one of the outcomes of D3.3. The risk evaluation approach will collect household survey data and contribute to the writing of a scientific paper on community-driven risk evaluation approach for Solutvyno. The final approach will collect information about the risk evaluation, the disaster risk preparedness and the place attachment. In addition, geo-referenced data will be collected to map the community perceptions on the land subsidence risk.

Teachers have been assigned to collect the household survey data, coordinate the collection of the data, motivate and provide guidance to the students in the data collection process, explain the parts in the questionnaire that may not be clear to some of the Solutvyno household, collate the data and forwarding it to TUD and write short reflection reports. The results will be shared through the HumTechLab) and ImProDiReT community as part of the dissemination activities of these organizations. The final outcome of D3.3 will be a verified and locally adopted multi-stakeholder risk evaluation approach. In addition, the risk evaluation approach will be documented and (remotely) communicated to the local partners.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation and Objectives

The main objective of Work Package 3 is to design, develop and verify a method for risk evaluation and decision making. The specific objective of D3.3 is to develop a community- based risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno municipality, that can later be replicated and used in other DRR projects. The specific activities that have been conducted or plan to be conducted under D3.3 are to:

1. **Activity 3.3.1: Workshop on Risk Evaluation (1st Platform Meeting).** Prior to the workshop detailed interviews with the various stakeholders in Kiev, Uzhhorod and Solotvyno were conducted in July and August 2018. The interviews provided input for D3.1, 3.2 and 3.3. Thereafter a workshop was held in Solotvyno, which brought together various stakeholders. The stakeholders examined the requirements for an appropriate risk evaluation approach. The result of the interactive workshop was an outline of the various elements that should be included the risk evaluation approach to ensure local adoption.
2. **Activity 3.3.2: Development of Risk evaluation approach.** Building on the previous work done under D3.1, 3.2 and 3.3e, this activity focused on the development of the risk evaluation approach. We also used the outcomes of previous project activities under various WPs as input and requirements for the design and implementation of the risk evaluation approach. The risk evaluation approach will be documented and (remotely) communicated to the local partners. The unique aspects of the Solotvyno case study requires a risk evaluation approach that incorporates multiple stakeholders. The approach towards developing the tailored evaluation is one of the outcomes of D3.3.
3. **Activity 3.2.3: Presentation and discussion risk evaluation approach (2nd Platform Meeting).** The developed risk evaluation approach, involving multiple stakeholders, will be presented at the 2nd platform meeting that may take place in November 2019. Prior to the presentation, the approach will be applied in Solotvyno, through the support of teachers and students aged 11-17 years. The approach is in the form of a household survey that will be implemented at every teachers and students aged 11-17 years households. In addition, each student will request two of their neighbours to complete the household survey.

During the DRR platform meeting the approach will be discussed with various stakeholders, including local actors. The workshop will serve as an evaluation and feedback point for the ongoing work in Work Package 3, and at the same time serve to ensure a knowledge transfer of the results thus far to the local community. The outcome of this activity will be a verified and locally adopted multi-stakeholder risk evaluation approach.

1.2 Relation to other WP 3 deliverables

The outcomes of WP3 focus on three main components:

1. Deliverable 3.1: A review of the state of the art (both within the scope of the project, as for the existing risk evaluation method);
2. Deliverable 3.2: A method to identify local requirement
3. Deliverable 3.3: A risk evaluation approach, building on the results of Work Package 1, and
4. Deliverable 3.4: A method for joint decision making to improve the community resilience building on the combined results of WP1 and WP2.

The combined outcomes of D3.1, D3.2, D3.3. and D3.4 will provide a novel method that builds on existing risk evaluation methods and adds the involvement of local community and stakeholders. The resulting interactive process is intended to support the embedment of knowledge in the various local organizations, raise the awareness in the local community and empower stakeholders to translate risk mapping into effective and comprehensive action.

The initial three WP3 deliverables are interconnected and inform one another, as illustrated in Figure 1. D3.4 is still at the prototype development stage and its relation with D3.1, D3.2, and D3.3 will be discussed at a latter stage when preparing the D3.4 report. The remaining part of this sub-section will discuss how D3.3 is related to D3.1 and 3.2.

Figure 1 Relation of D 3.3 to Previous WP3 Deliverables.

D3.1: State of the Art analysis

The analysis determined the current state of the art for both the risk evaluation (D3.3) and (joint) decision making approaches (D3.4). Furthermore, the local circumstances

(from WP4) were examined, providing specific requirements to be considered. The combined outcome of these activities, provided a thorough review of existing methods and best practices and identified which of these are applicable and if so, to what extent.

D3.2: An approach to identify local requirements

The analysis presented gaps between the existing approaches and the specific local needs, providing the necessary input for the development of new approaches and their evaluation criteria. The outcome of D3.2 was a list of elements of existing practices, frameworks and guidelines for both risk evaluation (D3.3) and (joint) decision making approaches (D3.4), that can be integrated with each other and are applicable to the local context.

D3.3 Risk evaluation approach

The current deliverable describes in detail the process of developing a tailored risk evaluation approach, based on the one hand on the local circumstances and on the other hand on the existing guidelines, will be described in this deliverable. This deliverable describes this process in two parts:

1. the generic approach followed to define and design the risk evaluation approach, and
2. the application of this approach to the local context including the resulting specific risk evaluation.

The deliverable will both a wider audience in describing and demonstrating the approach, as well as provide specific input for the further ImProDiReT project for use in other work packages, and in particular in WP4

1.3 The structure of this document

D3.3 is structured as follows: After this introduction, we explain the methodology that we used to design and implement (for the parts that are not yet implemented, how we plan to implement them) the risk evaluation approach. Then, we provide explanatory notes for three critical parts of the risk evaluation approach in 3-5. Section 3 discussed the conceptual framework for the risk evaluation approach (REA). It provides a detailed analysis of existing risk evaluation approaches and explains how we used these approaches to design a criterion for the Solotvyno REA. Section 4 deals with the first part of the risk evaluation approach, where three scales are explained and described. These three scales that form the initial part of the REA are the household demographic scale, the place attachment scale and the land subsidence preparedness scale. Next, section 5 introduces the risk matrix and how the REA is classified. D3.3 ends with brief concluding remarks (Section 6), and definitions of key terms (Section 7). The final part of the document contains the annexes and references.

2 Methodological Approach

Methodologically, D2.7 customizes the [Economic Research Centre’s Public Policy Design methodology](#), used to guide the policy formulation process, when there are:

- Different and/or conflicting interests;
- The users do not have a complete picture of the current problem and their required action; and
- There is no established, systematic, efficient and customized discourse process for the users to adopt in order to reach a consensus.

The methodology comprises of five phases:

1. the preliminary and planning phase;
2. situation analysis phase;
3. data collection and analysis phase;
4. policy design phase; and
5. involving social (interest) groups into discourse phase.

These five phases were readjusted to fit into the project objectives and a new methodological approach was developed as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Community-based Risk Evaluation Approach Methodology.

Key:

CREA Community-based Risk Evaluation Approach
 DMP Data Management Plan
 DPIA Data Privacy Impact Assessments
 GDPR General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679

HREC Human Research Ethics Committee
 REA Risk Evaluation Approach
 REDA Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach

2.1 Scoping

At this first stage, the important issues were discovered, mapped and discussed by the key stakeholders. Information was gathered by searches; collecting articles, news reports and literature; and by conducting meetings; workshops; and interviews. At this time existing communities are found and new ones start to form. Scoping has no time limit; it can take a few weeks, or can develop over years.

Key Participants

Community organisers, project team, community members and the public.

2.2 Community Building

The aim of Community Building is for all participants to come to a shared understanding of the issue (Land Subsidence), the project goals of the community-based risk evaluation and how to document activities. At this stage the skills of the participants were identified, and also others were brought on board for any missing skills or expertise. It became evident, at this phase that the most effective way to work with the community in Solotvyno was through the schools. Therefore, we held several meetings, in Solotvyno and Warsaw, Poland with the heads of the following schools, to support our efforts in Solotvyno community building:

- Romanian Secondary School of Solotvyno
- Ukrainian Secondary School of Solotvyno
- Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Solotvyno
- Romanian Lyceum of Solotvyno

The International Public Awareness Campaign Workshops were held on May 9-10, 2019 at the Main School of Fire Service (MSFS) in Warsaw, Poland. The aim of the workshops were, first of all, to create local leaders who will spearhead the awareness campaigns and, second, to provide awareness campaign tools for Uzhhorod region and Solotvyno area. The workshops were compatible with the 5 basic steps for conducting a public awareness campaign. The teachers developed plans under WP2 aimed at supporting the Solotvyno community to develop a shared understanding on security and safety issues related to land subsidence.

The workshop participants agreed on the following next steps:

- Describe their campaigns in detail;
- Implement an information campaign in individual regions;
- Develop leaflets, textbook and pre-guide in Hungarian and Romanian; and
- Organise a meeting in September with participants on the campaigns.

D3.3 used the already established networks under WP2 to conduct the risk evaluation approach. Thus, we contacted the English teachers from the main schools in Solotvyno and agreed to conduct the risk evaluation under their leadership and support.

Key Participants

Community organisers, School teachers, project team, community members and the public.

2.3 Developing the Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach (REDA)

Research indicates that different contexts require different risk evaluation approaches. There is limited research on the most feasible risk evaluation approach for a specific complex social-technical context. Also, there is limited guidance on how to develop a methodology to identify the best risk evaluation approach for a specific social-technical context. We developed the risk evaluation decision-aiding approach (REDA) that helps identify the best risk evaluation approach for a given situation. We used the case of Solotvyno to test the working of our developed approach. In order to identify the most suitable approach, we reviewed multiple existing approaches. After an intensive literature

review, we arrived at four possible risk evaluation approaches, namely: German Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU), the Th. Plattner approach, The predictive, Bayesian risk classification scheme (PBRC Scheme) and the Pollard approach. We made comparisons between the different approaches. After analysing each approach, we concluded that the two approaches: WBGU and PBRC, are the most suitable in the case of Solotvyno. The case study shows that the REDA works and is useful.

Annex C contains the detailed draft publication on the Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach (REDA).

Key Participants

Delft University of Technology

2.4 Community-based Risk Evaluation Approach (CREA) Survey Development

The purpose of the community-based risk evaluation approach (CREA) survey is to assess how to can make the Solotvyno community safe. The data will provide input for the community action plan to reduce risks associated to the collapse of the land near the salt mines. We will collect information about the risk evaluation, the disaster risk preparedness and the place attachment. In addition, geo-referenced data will be collected to map the community perceptions on the land subsidence risk. Processing and storing of your data will be handled in accordance with the European Union 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation. Participants will be invited to answer a set of questions about your perceptions of the land subsidence risk in Solotvyno municipality, your level of preparedness and how attached you are to the area. The estimated duration to answer the questions ranges from 15 - 30 minutes.

Annex D contains the detailed Community-based Risk Evaluation Approach (CREA) Survey.

Key Participants

Project team and reviewed by community organisers and community members.

2.5 Planning and TOR Development

The participants collectively decided on the project goals, on the risk evaluation strategies and on protocols for collecting data. This included a plan for collecting the household survey data. CREA was developed from existing resources, reviewed and now it is undergoing testing and soon it will be implemented. Participants will be taught how to collect the data either manually with printed questionnaires or online using the Qualtrics website (<https://login.qualtrics.com/login?lang=uk>).

Annex E contains the detailed Household Survey TOR for the Teachers.

Key Participants

Community organisers, English teachers, ARDZ and TUD.

2.6 Data Management Plan Development

The household survey will produce several data sets: the risk evaluation sub-scale dataset, the disaster risk preparedness subscale dataset and the place attachment dataset. In addition, geo-referenced data will be collected to map the community perceptions on the land subsidence risk. After the data is collected, a text-based format (or zipped version thereof) will be used, which is appropriate, given that reproducibility is one of the project purposes.

To better manage the project data, we developed a Data Management Plans (DMP) using [DMPonline](#). [DMPonline](#) is an online tool to help research teams write DMPs and to easily incorporate institutional resources and recommendations available to them. TU Delft adapted and customized DMPonline to provide TU Delft researchers with tailored guidance about TU Delft-specific support.

[DMPonline](#) portal has two options to choose from, since it is an EU project. However, ImProDiReT is not a H2020 project. Therefore, we adopted the choice of the European Research Council (ECR) template. The decision was made in consultation with TUD data steward and the TUD privacy team.

Annex F contains the detailed Solotvyno Municipality Data Management Plan (DMP).

Key Participants

TUD project team, TUD Data Steward and TUD Privacy Team.

2.7 Consent Form Development

Before agreeing to participate in the study, the participants will be given a printed copy of the informed consent form to read. After reading the explanation of the study (informed consent form), the participants answer the following questions by ticking either the “Yes” or “No” boxes:

1. I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked were answered to my satisfaction.
2. I voluntarily consent to be a participant in this study. I understand that I can refuse to answer questions and I can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason.

3. I understand that taking part in the study involves the risk of the interception of my personal data during the processing and storage of the information provided by me to complete this study. I furthermore understand that the researcher has minimized the risks by taking the appropriate measures of storage and access control to secure the sensitive data during and after the project.
4. I understand that the anonymized information (anonymized survey transcript) I provide will be used for publications and other research-related activities (e.g., reports, website, blogs, etc.).
5. I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me, where I live, will not be shared beyond the researcher and the PI.

The participants will also be requested to sign the informed consent form.

Annex G contains the detailed Solotvyno Municipality Household Survey Consent Form.

Key Participants

TUD project team, TUD Data Steward and TUD HREC Committee Team.

2.8 DPIA Exclusion and Approval to collect Personal / Sensitive Data

Processing and storing of your data will be handled in accordance with the European Union 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation. Participants are informed of their right to request access to, change or erasure of your personal data at any time. To get the DPIA exclusion, we agreed to the following:

1. Any personal sensitive data, such as names, identities, location, will be replaced, scrambled or blurred to ensure that anonymized data cannot be linked back to participants.
2. The anonymized data may be used for research and publications.
3. For the project duration (September 1 2019 - February 29, 2020), personal information will only be accessible to the project members (the Researcher a PI).
4. The data will be stored in the Netherlands and will never be made available to third parties.
5. After the project, the anonymized data and research results (non-personal) will be archived for a period of 10 years and will be accessible to anyone.
6. At the time of publication, the cleaned-up data will not include the Geo points, any personally identifiable information and all personal data.
7. The cleaned-up data will be made available on the 4TU website, with a DOI for the data used to generate the results in the paper.

The participants will be informed that the main risks of participating in the study are linked to the interception of their personal data during the processing and storage of the information provided by them, to complete the study. They will also be informed that the researcher has minimized the risks by agreeing to only use anonymized data that cannot be linked back to them and taking the appropriate measures of storage and access control to secure the sensitive data during and after the project. The data interception risks are

thus minimal. Finally, the participants will be assured that participation in the survey is otherwise safe for the participants.

Key Participants

TUD project team, TUD Data Steward and TUD Privacy Team.

2.9 Approval from the Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC)

Because TU Delft is concerned with maintaining ethical protections for those who volunteer to help our science and engineering studies, our own Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) examines research which involves human subjects. This screening is mandatory. Among the qualities expected of ethical human research, the committee considers:

1. Are subjects subjected to a greater than acceptable risk given the potential benefits?
2. Have subjects or participants been adequately informed and given free consent? Can they withdraw without any implications?
3. Are vulnerable populations targeted and have special precautions been taken to protect them?
4. Is the study properly expressed scientifically and does it clearly state its potential harms and benefits?
5. Is the equipment safe?
6. How will personal data be protected?

As with other Ethics Committees around the world, the HREC first uses a checklist to determine whether the proposed research poses more than a minimal risk. Minimal risk is typically defined by the standard, every-day risks we face in our daily lives. These applications are reviewed by the secretary and chair of HREC. This procedure takes about 2 weeks.

If the proposed study poses an apparently more than minimal risk, further submissions are requested, and the committee (composed of representatives of various faculties) convenes to assess the submission. Following the committee's discussion, changes may be requested to the proposed study's protocols, or more typically, to the informed consent documents. In some cases, no changes are necessary. Once approved, a letter is issued from the committee which is increasingly necessary for funding agencies and journal publications indicating that the study has been reviewed and approved. The committee meets every month (except during Summer holidays).

The committee reviewed the ImProDiReT checklist and approved the application on August 12, 2019 without any conditions and/or recommendations.

Annex H contains the detailed HREC Application and Approval Letter.

Key Participants

TUD project team, TUD Data Steward and TUD HREC Committee Team.

2.10 GDPR Compliance Survey Tool Scanning, Approval and Facilitation

Planning sees participants collectively decide on the project goals, on sensing strategies and on protocols for collecting data. This includes a plan for collecting other types of indicators. It is when the sensing tools are created or developed from existing resources and are tested and calibrated. Participants learn about sensors and are introduced to approaches for understanding data.

Key Participants

TUD project team, TUD Data Steward and TUD Privacy Team.

2.11 CREA Household Survey Data Collection

The process first begun by developing a draft risk evaluation approach. Then four teachers were selected to represent the four main schools. According to the Solotvyno schooling system, the primary and secondary and high school in one place – and they are all called secondary school. The various classes are grouped into primary, basic secondary education and high education. The classes are broken down as follows:

- Class 1 – 4 is primary (6-10 years)
- Class 5 – 9 is basic secondary education (11 – 15 years)
- Class 10 – 11 is high education – secondary (16 -17 years)

There is no University, Institutes or Vocational Schools in Solotvyno. Therefore, the four schools that will be targeted are:

- Romanian Secondary School of Solotvyno
- Ukrainian Secondary School of Solotvyno
- Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Solotvyno
- Romanian Lyceum of Solotvyno

The Solotvyno Boarding school was eliminated from the list of target schools because the families of the students are not from Solotvyno. The school consists of pupils from neighbouring villages, which is not the focus of the household survey. In addition, boarding students are restricted from leaving the school compound to conduct household surveys.

The lead teachers for every school will be the English teachers, apart from the Romanian Lyceum where we will work with the Head teacher. The English teachers were selected to ease communications and coordination exercises between TUD and the four schools. The risk evaluation questionnaires will be answered by:

1. All the teachers in the school;

2. The family member of each student between the ages 11-17 years (1 questionnaire per household). Please note that for siblings, only one household questionnaire will be filled for their household. However, each sibling will be encouraged to reach out to different neighbors and encourage them to fill the questionnaires; and
3. Neighbors of the students (one young family and one elderly family or if not possible any two neighbors). Teachers should encourage the students to select their respondents from diverse groups (age, gender, family setup, religion...).

Annex E contains the detailed Household Survey TOR for the Teachers, which explains how the survey will be implemented.

Key Participants

School teachers, school students aged 11 – 17 years and project team.

2.12 Presentation of Results (DRR Platform Meeting)

Using all the data and complementary indicators gathered during the sensing phase, the information is analysed and discussed amongst the community. Bringing this information together is important for identifying areas for action and change. The aim is to build a collective awareness from the data. The analysis stage can include activities such as data visualisation, and people from professional science or academia.

Key Participants

Community organisers, project teams a community member, data visualisers and external experts.

2.13 Action Planning, Appraisal and Reflection

The developed risk evaluation approach, involving multiple stakeholders, will be presented at the Solotvyno DRR platform meeting. During the meeting the approach will be discussed and applied involving the various stakeholders, including local actors. The workshop will serve as an evaluation and feedback point for the ongoing work in Work Package 3, and ensure a knowledge transfer of the results to the local community.

The aim of the Solotvyno DRR platform meeting is to devise, organise and deliver an action, or series of actions, that can generate recognition of the issue, make an impact and make change. Actions can range from an individual change to public-facing activities aimed at widening awareness, or even policy change. The Solotvyno DRR platform meeting will be organized and implemented under the leadership of the Resilience Advisory Network (RAN).

Participants will then reflect on the process, and consider what worked well and what could be improved. After the household survey reflection is concluded, TUD will provide small souvenirs with the project name for all the teachers and students in the 'graduation ceremony'. Depending on the available budget, TUD will select one or two possible souvenirs from the following proposed list:

1. Bag
2. Pencil case;
3. Pen; or
4. Calendar / Note Book.

To motivate the schools, each souvenir will be printed with the name of the school, as follows:

- Romanian Secondary School of Solotvyno;
- Ukrainian Secondary School of Solotvyno;
- Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Solotvyno; and
- Romanian Lyceum of Solotvyno.

Key Participants

Community organisers, project teams, community members, media outlets and government officials.

2.14 Legacy

A legacy is created by looking towards the future of the project and making a plan for lasting impact. Under WP6, the project will develop plans to share the information through Facebook, the website, Leaflets and the iSolotvyno Magazine, to ensure that the project is sustainable, the project's tools are being reused, and uptake continues. This is also the phase for writing scientific publications from the data collected, as well as for sharing project data through the 4TU.Centre for Research Data, that might be useful for other initiatives. This risk evaluation approach will be widely disseminated together with REDA and CREA, so that other projects can use the tools developed under the project.

Key Participants

Community organisers, project teams, community members, academics and external experts.

3 Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach (REDA)

3.1 Introduction

There are many different definitions of risk by researchers from diverse disciplines. By some, it is the likelihood of occurrence of an event [3], for others, it is the consequences of an event [3, 4] while others combine the two elements [1]. Other researchers define risk as uncertainty about the occurrence of an event and the damage that might be incurred [5]. Various researchers propose one common definition that entails both the likelihood of occurrence of an event and its possible consequences [3, 5]. By combining these descriptions, we define risk as the likelihood of an event occurring and the severity of its consequences. To clarify this definition, we provide two examples, as follows:

1. The likelihood of dying because of a plane crash is so low that it is almost pointless to quantify. However, the consequences in terms of loss of life, economic losses coupled with the environmental impacts, are extremely large; hence, it is still perceived as a risk.
2. The likelihood of a child falling during their first bicycle ride is high; however, the consequence is may not be severe. In this case, it is also perceived as a risk because the likelihood is high.
3. A person may decide to accept the risk of dying in a plane, or a child may decide to accept the risk of falling during their first bicycle ride. These decisions are known as risk-taking decisions. Risk evaluation is known as the process of deciding whether to accept, tolerate or avoid a risk. In this paper, we define risk evaluation as making judgments regarding the tolerability and acceptability of a particular risk, depending on whether risk reduction measures are needed.

Risk evaluation is the third phase in risk governance [1]. The four phases of risk governance are pre-assessment, risk-appraisal, risk evaluation and risk management. Figure 3 visualizes this process.

Figure 3. IRGC Risk Governance Framework. (Source: Ortwin Renn, 2005).

The main goal of risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and the acceptability of a given risk, based on the scientific evidence collected in the risk appraisal phase and societal values [1, 6-8]. Tolerability refers to a willingness to live with a particular risk as long as taking the risk is worth it and the risk is adequately controlled [9]. Acceptability only occurs when there is no need to take risk reduction measures to ensure safety [10]. Risk reduction measures only apply to tolerable risks. Acceptable risks do not require risk reduction measures. In the case of intolerable risks, the risk reduction measures outweigh the benefits of tolerating the specific risk.

Risk evaluation takes place after risk appraisal and before risk management. Risk appraisal contains two sub-phases: risk assessment and concern assessment. At the risk assessment sub-phase, the identification, describing, mapping and analysing of each hazard takes place according to its likelihood of occurrence and its consequences should a disaster occur. Afterwards, we assessed exposure and vulnerability and estimated whether the risk is high, moderate or low [7]. Analysing vulnerability takes place during the concern assessment sub-phase and entails risk perceptions, social concerns and socio-economic impacts. Thus, the risk appraisal phase gathers evidence on the hazard (risk assessment), exposure (risk assessment) and vulnerability (concern assessment).

Risk evaluation is a sub-phase of the tolerability and acceptability judgement phase and occurs before risk characterisation. In categorisation the creating of risk profiles take place, judgments on the seriousness of risk are made, and risk reduction options are taken into consideration. After the judgement of tolerability and acceptability, risk management takes place. Tolerability and acceptability judgments are critical in deciding whether there is a need for risk reduction measures.

Research indicates that individual risk-taking decisions are dependent on the nature of the risk and the societal context [11-15]. A person may choose to avoid, accept, transfer, mitigate or exploit a risk, based on the likelihood and consequences of the risk and their social context [13]. Kasperson [11] explain that the context a person is in affects their decision and preferences. Müller and Rau [13], conclude that the social context, the societal preferences and the level of heterogeneity of a particular risk affects the individual decision whether or not to take the risk. This research demonstrates that “people’s choices are not only context-dependent but are sensitive to their degree of inequality aversion” [13], (p. 116). Li and Yu [12] explain context-dependent choice using the foraging theory to explain the persistence of choice behaviour and provide insights regarding “unchosen alternatives” [12], (p. 170). Therefore, choosing a specific risk evaluation approach for a particular social context may be better than using the same approach in any context.

Furthermore, in some social contexts determining the likelihood and consequences of a particular risk is highly uncertain. These social contexts are known as complex socio-technical systems. Onencan [16], (p. 1) explains that “socio-technical systems emphasise social (actors, networks, organisations) and technical systems, in the design, analysis and systems operation.” According to Sheard [17] complex systems

“do not have a centralising authority and are not designed from a known specification, but instead involve disparate stakeholders creating systems that are functional for other purposes and are only brought together in the complex system because the individual “agents” of the system see such cooperation as being beneficial for them.”

The main question that we seek to answer in this particular section is: “How do you develop a methodology to identify the best risk evaluation approach for a specific social-technical context?”. To answer the research question, we developed an approach to identify the best risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno. Due to the different existing approaches, there must also be a method that guides DRR-experts in choosing one. The purpose of this paper is to design this method.

In order to find a suitable risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno, we analysed multiple existing approaches and selected four possible risk evaluation approaches that matched our definition.

These four approaches are the approach by the German Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU), the Th. Plattner approach, The predictive, Bayesian risk classification scheme (PBRC scheme) approach and the Pollard approach [6, 18-20]. The four approaches were compared based on various criteria, and two approaches: WBGU and the PBRC Scheme were found to be most suitable for Solutvyno municipality. The results are useful for direct application, in the case of Solutvyno, regarding the subsidence risk. However, the methodology can also be used by researchers to identify the most feasible risk evaluation approach for a particular socio-technical context.

3.2 Towards a Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Criteria

The goal of risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and the acceptability of a given risk [6]. To determine which approach is most applicable for a given socio-technical context, the different approaches must be assessed to decide whether they aid in reaching the primary goal for the evaluation for that particular context. Most DRR experts use a criterion to determine the tolerability and acceptability of a risk [21-23]. Those criteria are useful for defining the exact format of the parameters used for decision making [24]. Use of criteria is preferred by DRR experts who seek clarity and structure to present the results and their analysis. We selected to use the risk acceptance criteria to present the results, including the comparisons between the different approaches.

To be able to assess the approaches with the use of risk acceptance criteria, firstly the existing risk acceptance criteria will be explained. Various researchers came up with risk evaluation criteria that, according to their research, should be included in an approach in order to correctly evaluate risk. We used the risk evaluation criteria of 3 researchers to develop the ImProDiReT project risk evaluation criteria, namely:

1. The Health and Safety Executive criterion (HSE criterion)[25];
2. Vrijling, Hengel and Houben criterion [26]; and
3. Kasperson criterion [10].

To arrive at an extensive set of criteria, we included all three of the studies above. After compiling all the criterion from the three studies, we ended up with a total of 9 risk acceptance criteria. We have merged the corresponding criteria to create a clear structure. Figure 4 shows which criterion are merged.

Figure 4. Merging of the criteria

We identified nine elements combined into three criteria. The aim is not to find the approach that includes the most elements, but the approach that includes all the most critical elements for a specific socio-technical context. In section 5 we will explain this further with the help of a case study.

3.3 Materials and Methods

In this method section, we have extensively described the steps we took to develop the methodology, the choices we made and the rationale. This study used a systematic literature review in order to investigate past research that developed a qualitative risk evaluation approach. It was decided to focus on non-mathematical approaches so that the research did not become too extensive and we were able to finish it in the given time. During a systematic literature review, it is imperative to stay critical and focused because not all sources and articles are reliable [27].

We first looked up and compared different definitions of risk. Then we derived a set of keywords that we chose to use as consistent search terms when searching all resources [27]. The search terms we have used are: risk (A1), risk definition (A2), risk probability (A3), risk consequence (A4), define risk (A5) and what is a risk (A6).

After defining risk, we needed to explain the risk governance framework, so we searched for risk articles that included a detailed explanation of this process. We decided to use one of the articles that we already found during our search for definitions of risk.

In order to compare different community-based risk evaluation approaches, we had to find the existing approaches. We used a third set of search terms to find articles on community-based risk evaluation approaches. This last set consists of the search terms: risk evaluation approaches (B1), community-based risk evaluation (B2), community-based risk evaluation approaches (B3), risk

evaluation methods (B4) and criteria for evaluating risk (B5). To narrow down the publications, We have combined those terms with disaster, hazard or natural hazard.

In order to find studies about the risk, we have used five different electronic databases, namely:

1. Google Scholar
2. Scopus
3. ScienceDirect
4. SpringerLink
5. JSTOR.

We used those databases because all of them contain a lot of scientific papers that can be of great value to our research. Table 1 summarises all the strategies used for finding evaluation approaches and the outcome.

Table 1. Search strategies for evaluation approaches.

Keywords	Databases	Search Outcome	Last date of search
("risk evaluation approaches" OR "community-based risk evaluation" OR "community-based risk evaluation approaches" OR "risk evaluation methods" OR "criteria for evaluating risk") AND ("disaster" OR "natural hazards" OR "hazards")	Google scholar	1010	01/05/2019
	Science direct	190	
	Springer Link	177	
	Scopus	74	
	JSTOR	5	

In total, we obtained 1456 publications from searching for electronic databases. To filter the right articles from the first set of publications, a selection was made based on the title of the publications. We looked at whether the title was related to the research subject.

Establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria for study participants is a standard, required practice when designing high-quality research protocols [28]. Table 2 presents the inclusion and exclusion criteria used for this systematic review. There was no restriction applied to the date of studies sampled, and we searched all databases for studies published up to 01/05/2019.

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion / Exclusion	Criteria
Inclusion criteria	Publications must be peer-reviewed Publications that describe risk evaluation and not risk analysis or risk identification Publications that describe a specific usable approach
Exclusion criteria	Publications that describe a part of risk assessment that is too specific Publications that are not written in Dutch or in English Publications that are only available as abstract

To make sure the articles are valid and reliable, we restricted the search to peer-reviewed articles. Furthermore, because we are researching risk evaluation approaches, the approaches must be risk evaluation approaches and not risk assessment approaches. To assess whether an approach was for risk evaluation, we checked whether the approach considered the evidence only or evidence and values. We also eliminated the publications that were not Dutch or English and the articles that we could not access the full copy while scanning the titles. Abstract only articles were excluded because we needed a detailed explanation of the different approaches.

After this step, the number of relevant publications reduced from 1456 to 40. We then read the abstract of all 40 articles, and on that basis, we selected the relevant articles. After reading all the abstracts and eliminating unsuitable publications based on the exclusion criteria, we arrived at only 12 articles. Because 12 articles are relatively few, we decided to use the snowballing method.

We started with backward snowballing, which means identifying relevant publications from the reference list of the most relevant publication that passed the quality assessment step. When we finished backward snowballing, we applied forward snowballing [29]. Forward snowballing implies checking the publications that cite publications that are considered relevant and passed the assessment step. All the papers that we found through snowballing underwent the same assessment step, as mentioned earlier in the section.

After the snowballing, we had 23 articles found via the search terms and four articles extra that we came across during the research. Those remaining articles' full texts were read to arrive at the final selection. Figure 5 is a visualisation of the selection process.

Figure 5. Article selection flow chart

Some of the publications we found include a risk evaluation approach. We also searched for requirements for an effective risk evaluation approach. Therefore, we searched for publications that included criteria that are used for determining the tolerability and the acceptability of risk. Using the search term “risk acceptance criteria,” we found three relevant and peer-reviewed articles. We selected nine sub-criteria to use for determining the tolerability and the acceptability of risk comprising of three main criteria. After that, we analysed whether each of the nine elements were included in the different risk evaluation approaches. Those elements are placed in the rows of table 6, and the approaches are the columns. When we concluded that an approach takes an element into account, we placed a checkmark in the row of that element.

3.4 Results

Table 3 shows the risk evaluation approaches that we encountered during the literature review. All the approaches use of a variety of criterion to evaluate a given risk. These approaches can be considered as risk evaluation approaches because they do contain de societal aspects as well as the technical aspects of risk.

Table 3. Risk Evaluation Approaches

Approach	Main factors	Reference
WBGU	Nine criteria: Extent of damage, Probability of occurrence, Extent of damage, Incertitude, Ubiquity, Persistency, Reversibility, Delay effect, Violation of equity, Potential of mobilisation	Klinke and Renn [6]ke and Renn [6]
Th. Plattner approach	Six criteria: Voluntariness, Reducibility, Knowledge, Endangerment, Extent of damage, Frequency of event	Plattner [20]
PBRC Scheme	Nine characteristics: Potential consequences, Uncertainty about consequences, Ubiquity, Persistency, Delay effect, Reversibility, Violation of equity, Potential of mobilisation and the difficulty in establishing appropriate performance measures.	Kristensen, Aven [18]
Pollard approach	Seventeen criteria: Stock at Risk, Knock-on Effects, Spatial Extent, Heterogeneity, Spatial Extent, Sensitivity of Receptor, Severity of Effect, Temporal Extent, Latency, Accumulation, Reversibility, Scarcity, Notoriety, Unfairness, Imposition, Distrust.	Pollard, Davidson [19]

3.4.1 Klinke and Renn WBGU Criteria

Klinke and Renn included more criteria than the classic components such as the extent of damage and the probability of occurrence. To find more criteria they looked into the researches of Boholm in 1998, Sjöberg in 1999, Slovic in 1987 and 1992 and Rohrmann & Renn in 2000. The result was a long list of criteria that was not identical for different groups. The WBGU had addressed this problem by involving many experts in finding the most suitable criteria. These criteria ended up to be: the extent of damage, probability of occurrence, the extent of damage, incertitude, ubiquity, persistency, reversibility, delay effect, violation of equity and potential of mobilisation. The extent of damage is about the adverse effects in, for example, the number of deaths or the number of injured. The probability of occurrence is an estimate for the relative frequency of a discrete or continuous loss function. Incertitude is the umbrella term for all uncertain components. Ubiquity indicates the degree of the geographical spread of potential damages and persistency indicates the degree of temporal spread of potential damages. By reversibility we mean the possibility to restore the situation to the state before the damage occurred. The delay effect describes the delay between the activity and the actual impact of that activity. Violation of equity is about the discrepancy between those who enjoy the benefits and those who bear the risks.

Klinke and Renn divided the potential of mobilisation criteria into four major elements:

1. Inequity and injustice associated with the distribution of risks and benefits over time, space, and social status (thus covering the criterion of equity).
2. Psychological stress and discomfort associated with the risk or the risk source (as measured by psychometric scales).
3. Potential for social conflict and mobilisation (degree of political or public pressure on risk regulatory agencies).
4. regulatory agencies).
5. Spill-over effects that are likely to be expected when highly symbolic losses have repercussions on other fields such as financial markets or loss of credibility in management institutions.

3.4.2 Th. Plattner approach

In his research, Plattner suggests that evaluation criteria can be used to compute the perceived individual risk and acceptable individual risk. The factors he found focuses on natural hazard risk perception on the individual level. We compiled the list of factors based on the literature on risk perception. The factors were then presented to a group of experts who selected the most relevant factors. The factors found are as follows: voluntariness, reducibility, knowledge, endangerment, the extent of damage and frequency of the event. Some of those factors have a slightly more extensive meaning; Table 4 shows what each factor represents.

Table 4. Th. Plattner evaluation criteria

Evaluation criteria	Represents
Voluntariness	Voluntariness
Reducibility	Reducibility Predictability Avoidability
Knowledge	Familiarity Knowledge about risk Manageability
Endangerment	Controllability Number of people affected Fatality of consequences Distribution of victims Scope of area affected Immediacy of effects Directness of impact
Extent of damage	Extent of damage
Frequency of event	Frequency of event

3.4.3 PBRC Scheme

Kristensen and Aven criticised the WBGU approach of Klinke and Renn. Their main point of critique was related to the understanding and meaning of what risk is. Kristensen and Aven present a Bayesian risk classification schema based on the WBGU schema, which they believe therefore is considered as a modified version of the WBGU schema. The PBRC schema consists of nine characteristics. Some of the characteristics are taken directly from the WBGU schema, some are modified, and some are new. The nine proposed characteristics are potential consequences, uncertainty about consequences, ubiquity, persistency, delay effect, reversibility, violation of equity, the potential of mobilisation and the difficulty in establishing appropriate performance measures.

The two characteristics: potential consequences and uncertainty about consequences are the two key characteristics, while the other seven characteristics are used to describe aspects of these two characteristics. The potential consequence is indicated with observable quantities like the number of fatalities or the number of injuries. Factors such as variability in humans, animals, plants and technical systems; systematic and random measurement errors within the data used as background information; indeterminacy resulting from a genuine stochastic relationship between cause and effects etc. should all be taken into consideration when assessing the uncertainty about consequences.

A new characteristic that Kristensen and Aven included is the difficulty in establishing appropriate performance measures. This characteristic is included in order to represent this aspect of risk assessment. They recommend qualitatively describing this characteristic so the experts can give their opinion about the appropriateness of the selected quantities or measures on a scale from, for example, 0 to 10.

3.4.4 Pollard approach

The Pollard approach consists of 17 attributes that are classified according to those characterising the physical properties of the harm and those characterising the social response or valuation of the harm. We will briefly explain each of those attributes in Table 5.

Table 5. Explanations of the Pollard attributes

Attribute	Explanation
Stock at Risk	Represents a valuation of the overall harm, either in economic terms or in terms of numbers of receptors.
Knock-on Effects	Reflects that harm to one receptor may affect the wellbeing of another receptor.
Spatial Extent	Denotes the overall area in which exposures to the hazard that causes environmental harm are experienced.
Heterogeneity	Reflects that within the overall area denoted by Spatial Extent, there may be heterogeneity in exposure to the hazard.
Sensitivity of Receptor	Reflects the proportion of receptors exposed that exhibit the harm.
Severity of Effect	Defines the general physical effect on an individual sensitive receptor only.
Temporal Extent	Denotes the length of time that the environmental harm will be experienced.
Latency	The period of time before the consequent environmental harm starts to be realized during the hazard.
Accumulation	The changes in rate at which the harm progresses over time.
Reversibility	Considers both whether the effects of the harm are reversible and, if so, over what time scale.
Scarcity	Reflects the abundance of the receptor, used to consider the loss of cultural resources, and physical environments.
Dread	Reflects that society can have an aversion to, or fear of, a harm that may be largely unrelated to its physical nature.
Unfamiliarity	Gives an assessment of concern that may arise out of a low degree of knowledge and understanding of the harm.
Notoriety	Reflects the potential for raised awareness, and anxiety about harm via the media and other channels and information.
Unfairness	Reflects the discontent that may arise from the inequity or unfairness of a harm's distribution.
Imposition	Measures the social value afforded by the degree of personal control over the harm.
Distrust	Captures the consequences of lack of trust in characterisation of the harm or in those responsible for its management.

In order to see which approach scores on which criteria, we formulated an element for each of the criterion (Table 6). We ended up with the following set of elements: Does the approach include/consider?

1. the cost/benefit character? (U1)
2. the costs related to risk reduction? (U2)
3. the magnitude of associated benefits? (U3)
4. a criterion specifically focused on not passing a maximum? (E1)
5. a criterion that compares the risk with other risks prevalent in society? (E2)
6. a criterion that takes the degree of voluntariness to account? (E3)
7. a criterion that compares the risk with the risk level during the natural background? (T1)
8. a criterion that focuses on existing solutions? (T2)
9. a criterion that also looks at the risks of available substitutes? (T3)

Table 6. Results of Applying the Risk Evaluation Methodology

Approaches		WBGU	Th. Plattner approach	PBRC Scheme	Pollard approach
Utility-based criterion	U1	✓		✓	✓
	U2	✓	✓	✓	✓
	U3	✓		✓	
Equity-based criterion	E1	✓		✓	
	E2		✓		✓
	E3	✓	✓	✓	✓
Technology-based criterion	T1		✓	✓	
	T2	✓	✓	✓	
	T3				

Table 6 gives a structured and organised way of which elements each approach includes. The WBGU approach and the PBRC Schema contain the most elements. The Th. Plattner approach focuses more on the equity-based criterion and the technology-based criterion and does not cover the utility-based criterion. The Pollard approach does not contain any element of the technology-based criterion but scores good on the utility-based criterion and the equity-based criterion.

3.4.5 Solotvyno Case study

In this paper we use a case study to demonstrate the developed REDA. We chose to use a case study because “the knowledge accumulates not around the original case but around the potentially more generic phenomena that was discovered or explained in the original case study” [30]. This means that we can not only find out if the method works for Solotvyno but for other contexts as well. Solotvyno municipality, which is the selected case study in this paper, qualifies as a complex socio-technical context because of the following qualities:

Every case has its own set of essential elements that should be included in the risk evaluation approach [13]. The aim is not to find the approach that includes the most elements, but the approach that includes all the most critical elements for Solotvyno municipality. That is why it is crucial that we first explain how unique Solotvyno is and why it is necessary to look for a specific approach.

We selected Solotvyno because of its specific socio-technical situation. It is a small village situated in the Tyachiv district of the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine that faces the risk of land subsidence due to the flooding of the salt domes. It is located close to the border with Romania, on the right bank of the Tisza River. The Carpathian sea deposited kilometres of high-quality salt many megannums ago [31]. Since the 1790s, salt has been mined in this area [32]. This process remained uninterrupted because there was clay protecting the upper part of the salt-dome [33]. To enable salt mining in the upper part of the salt-dome, the mining company removed the protective layer. In 1908 water began to filtrate the galleries, thereby dissolving the salt leading to flooding in the salt-mines [31]. This led to the formation of Lake Cunegunda [32]. The mines flooded and the water slowly moved into the cavities, dissolving the salt and the land slowly subsided. As a result of the eroded rock salt domes the ground subsided, and in some parts collapsed, leading to deformation of several houses [32]. Looking at those consequences, it becomes clear that the salt mining has created certain risks. Because of this risk, risk evaluation is needed to judge the acceptability and tolerability.

One key challenge facing disaster risk reduction (DRR) is decision science neither provides guidance nor a universally accepted methodology to select a suitable risk evaluation approach, for a particular complex socio-technical system [34]. While we know that different social-technical contexts need different risk evaluation approaches, it is difficult for DRR experts to choose between various existing methods. Also, though various risk evaluation approaches exist, very few have been tried and tested in various complex socio-technical contexts.

Hence, the risk is created by various actors who sometimes benefit from this risk while other people living in Solotvyno bear the risks. The fact that people benefiting are benefitting from the risk makes the case more complex, and that is why it requires a particular approach. When an actor concludes that it is more beneficial to take the risk, he accepts the risks and tries to manage it instead of mitigating it [35].

The criteria of costs related to risk reduction is vital for Solotvyno as well [31]. Even more important are the costs of filling the created holes, reclaiming the land and removing the objects that have remained of the mining shafts. Therefore, the costs related to risk reduction do have a significant impact on the risk level in Solotvyno.

The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits is also particularly relevant for the Solotvyno case. is due to approximately the same reason as with the first element, namely the fact that some people benefit from the cause of the risk.

The degree of voluntariness element also has to be considered because some inhabitants accepted the risk by continuing to either live or conduct business in the high-risk zones. Even though the inhabitants are free to move wherever they want, their options are limited if they cannot

find a job, a suitable school or place of worship, in the new place, so they choose to stay in Solotvyno. Mishra et al. [36] created a place attachment scale, which consists of 18 items to assess the level that a person is attached to a specific place. These elements in the scale explain various reasons why the Solotvyno inhabitants could choose to stay.

The place attachment indicators show that most of the current Solotvyno inhabitants prefer not to leave their current environment [37]. Because there may be cases where individuals and groups accept the risk when serious risk reduction measures have to be taken, this risk is a problem.

3.4.6 Most suitable approach for Solotvyno

To find out which approach is most applicable to the Solotvyno case, we must analyse the approaches on their strengths and weaknesses, and then the best fit for the Solotvyno must be determined. The most relevant elements for Solotvyno are the following:

1. The cost/benefit character;
2. The costs of risk reduction;
3. The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits;
4. Degree of voluntariness; and
5. Existing solutions.

In order to pick the best approach for the Solotvyno case, we assessed which approach contained most of these elements (Table 7).

Table 7. IRGC Assessment of the Five Elements in relation to Solotvyno

Approaches	WBGU	Th. Plattner approach	PBRC Scheme	Pollard approach
The cost/benefit character	✓		✓	✓
The cost of risk reduction	✓	✓	✓	✓
The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits	✓		✓	
Degree of voluntariness	✓	✓	✓	✓
Existing solutions	✓	✓	✓	

Table 7 shows that two approaches meet all the requirements of a sound risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno. These are the WBGU approach and the PBRC scheme approach. Because the PBRC Scheme contains one extra element that is considered essential for effective risk evaluation, we conclude that the PBRC Scheme is the most suitable approach for Solotvyno. During our research, we encountered a few striking findings. We will explain all the findings, the assumptions and limitations and the suggested future research in the discussion section.

3.5 Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach (REDA)

3.5.1 Generic REDA

There are various different risk evaluation approaches that are all suitable for different kinds of situations [6, 18-20]. To be able to select an approach it is important to first gain knowledge about the situation where risk evaluation must be carried out. In this paper we used the case of Solotvyno to test our developed REDA. In this discussion we will focus on a detailed explanation of our method

first, then we will discuss the application on Solotvyno and we conclude with limitations of the research.

Little guidance can be found about how to choose between different existing risk evaluation approaches. Because one approach can be much more suitable for a situation than another approach, finding a decision-aiding approach is very useful. The question we sought to answer in this paper is therefore: “How do you develop a methodology to identify the best risk evaluation approach for a specific social technical context?”. During this research we developed the REDA, that acts as guidance on how to select a suitable risk evaluation approach for a specific case. We tested our method on the unique case of Solotvyno and concluded that the REDA can support a lot of guidance in choosing a risk evaluation approach. The REDA contains 4 steps, namely: literature review, selecting priority criteria, risk evaluation criteria and ranking risk evaluation approaches. To give a better understanding of the process we provided a visualization in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Generic REDA

First a literature review must be performed. By defining a set of search terms that describe the wanted risk evaluation approaches, a systematic search for articles including risk evaluation approaches can be conducted. When the useful articles are selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the risk evaluation articles have to be separated from the risk assessment articles. It must therefore be considered here whether the focus is on acceptability and tolerability and not on identification or estimation. With too few found articles, the snowballing method can be used. Then again, the risk evaluation articles have to be distinguished from the risk assessment articles. The last step of the literature review is picking the actual approaches from the articles and describing them in detail. An extensive explanation is needed for a good analyzation in the last step.

The next step is selecting the specific priority criteria for the chosen case study. In order to do so the risk assessment report and the concern assessment report have to be analyzed. After the analyzation the current situation has to be compared with the reports. The contradictions between the reality and the reports have to be identified and explained further with information found during

a subsequent literature review. Place attachment also plays an important role in selecting priority criteria and therefore has to be reviewed. Finally, the current situation has to be compared with the 9 risk evaluation criteria to compile a list of priority criteria for the case study.

The aforementioned risk evaluation criteria are established by combining multiple risk evaluation criteria into groups. The more general risk evaluation criteria of HSE have been chosen as grouping criteria. Although the criteria from Vrijling et al. [26] and Kasperson [10] are only about risk acceptability, we considered them as useful because they were grouped into the HSE criteria and those do take tolerability into account. The criteria that are grouped under the utility-based criterion are all focused on either costs or benefits or both of them. Under the equity-based criterion we grouped the elements with the emphasis on the rights and feelings of individuals. The third criteria about technology includes elements regarding to existing solutions and any new related risks.

At last the found approaches have to be ranked based on how many priority criteria they include. All evaluation criteria must be checked for each approach. As guidance on how to decide whether an approach includes an element we composed a checklist (See Annex C).

3.5.2 Application of REDA to Solotvyno

As described above, we started with a literature review to select risk evaluation approaches that work with criteria. We ended up with 4 risk evaluation approaches: the WBGU, the Th. Plattner approach, the PBRC Schema and the Pollard approach. Thereafter we conducted a study on Solotvyno to be able to select the priority criteria. The risk in Solotvyno is a consequence of the mining of salt. It becomes clear from that, that there are costs and benefits associated with this risk. Furthermore, there are various costs associated with reducing this risk. The Ukrainian government had an attempt to move the most critical and under direct impact population to the neighbouring vicinity, and even constructed houses and infrastructure, but the population never moved. Removing all residents is not a very suitable option because people are attached to their place of residence and because these people cannot get jobs in other places just like that. Based on this information, we have selected 5 priority criteria for the case of Solotvyno, which are as follows: the cost/benefit character, the cost of risk reduction, the risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits, degree of voluntariness and existing solutions.

During the selection of priority criteria, we also searched for risk evaluation criteria prepared by experts. These two steps are carried out in parallel because the formulation of the risk priority criteria and the risk evaluation criteria must correspond in order to draw a conclusion. We found 9 risk evaluation criteria which experts believe are necessary for a good approach [10, 25, 26]. Subsequently we carried out the final step, starting with analysing the four approaches. The risk evaluation approach that contains the most priority criteria can be considered most suitable for the case.

In our case the two approaches: WBGU and PBRC schema both include all the priority criteria. To reach a conclusion, non-priority criteria can be considered. The PBRC schema contains one extra element of comparing the risk with the risk level during the background. If there are enough resources to implement this element, this approach can be seen as the best because it includes all the priority criteria and one extra risk evaluation element relative to the WBGU approach.

3.5.3 Separating risk evaluation approaches from risk appraisal approaches

Although the risk appraisal phase and the tolerability and acceptability judgement phases are two different phases in the framework, the terms are often used incorrectly. While looking for risk

evaluation approaches, we have often come across risk appraisal approaches. The search terms we used are only about evaluation, and they do not mention risk appraisal. We selected all the articles with approaches that were labelled risk evaluation approaches and ended up with quite a few articles. However, after thoroughly studying the articles, we found out that most of the approaches we found with these terms were about risk appraisal. The term risk evaluation is often used incorrectly to indicate risk appraisal methods.

The goal of risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and acceptability of a given risk. Risk appraisal entails assessing the identification and estimation of hazards. The use of wrong terms made searching for risk evaluation methods more complex. More than once we incorporated a risk appraisal method in our research by mistake, which we eliminated when we concluded that it was not a real risk evaluation approach. For well executed research with risk evaluation approaches as the main subject, there must be the certainty that it is actually about risk evaluation and not about risk appraisal. To be sure of this, every approach was checked several times to see if it was about acceptability and tolerability, and not about assessing risk.

3.5.4 Assumptions and limitations

The four-risk evaluation approaches we picked are criteria-based methods. To decide whether an approach met an element, we read the criteria with their explanations, if there was an explanation. However, none of the articles explained the criteria in great detail. As a result, it was difficult to estimate whether certain elements are included in an approach.

It was a limitation to arrive at the best risk evaluation because there is no full information about each approach. Because not every criterion was explained in detail, assumptions had to be made about if an approach did include an element or not. We applied the same assumptions to all approaches so that the assessment would be fair.

In more detail – Draft Publication on REDA (Annex C)

We have enclosed more detailed guidance on how to select the right risk evaluation approach for other future projects and later provided detailed explanation how REDA was applied in the case of Solotvyno. The draft still needs more refinement before it is published.

4 Place Attachment & Land Subsidence Preparedness

4.1 Introduction

This section will focus on three scales that have been used to develop the risk evaluation approach: the demographic profile scale, the place attachment scale and the land subsidence preparedness scale. The demographic scale is important in collecting basic demographics about the area of study that could not be found in our visit to the Solotvyno municipality in August 2018. The other two scales seek to answer the following research question: do peoples' attachment to a place coupled by their emotional association and relations to a particular environment affect land subsidence risk preparedness? The initial part of the risk evaluation approach seeks to assess this question with reference to Solotvyno municipality in the Transcarpathian region, Ukraine.

We selected the place attachment and flood preparedness scales developed by Mishra et. al [38]. The place attachment scale by Mishra et. al [38]. is divided into three forms of attachment to a place, namely, genealogical, economic and religious. Based on the specialized situation in Solotvyno, we customized both the place attachment scale and the flood preparedness scale, to develop part of the risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno. The place attachment modification took account of the uniqueness of the border town, which is multi-ethnic (national), multi-lingual, multi-religious, and located on top of salt domes. The flood preparedness scale was modified to address land subsidence risks instead of flooding. selected the place attachment

4.2 Place Attachment and Land Subsidence Preparedness

Mishra et. al [38], defines the concept of place attachment as “the emotional bond between individuals, groups, or communities, and their physical environments” [38], (p. 187). In the recent past, the connectedness of people to their environment and whether it has an effect on disaster risk preparedness and reduction, has been a key of scientific research [38-47].

Place attachment provides a sense of security and comfort, that may be real or false comfort and security that may stop them from taking the necessary actions to be prepared in case there is a disaster [38, 48]. Research indicates that these bonds to a particular place have a strong effect on disaster preparedness, evacuation and relocation [38]. In this research, we seek to explore the extent of place attachment to Solotvyno municipality and its effect on land subsidence preparedness.

Research has uncovered the connection between place attachment and:

1. Flood preparedness [38]
2. Climate change adaptation [43]
3. Wildfire mitigation [39]
4. Earthquake preparedness [49]
5. Landslides preparedness [50, 51]
6. Pro-environmental behaviors at tourist sites [52, 53]

Ethnographic research also indicates strong attachments of the Solotvyno community to the border town and: [54-56] and lists some of the factors, including:

1. The inhabitants are of mixed origin, and Soltvyno is the only place that they do not feel the pressure to integrate. The municipality governance structure has taken account of the complexity of its inhabitants and supported the emergence of nationality-based schools, multiple religious places and
2. The main burial site is on a hill where most of the inhabitant's forefathers are buried, and they need proximity to the place to visit their deceased loved ones regularly and later would like to be buried next to their forefathers. Relocation would reduce the chances of being buried with their family, and they cannot move with their deceased loved ones.
3. Its proximity to the Romanian-Ukrainian border, which provides a livelihood to some of them through cross-border trade.
4. The inhabitants have friends and relatives living there who provide emotional and financial support.
5. The inhabitant's own houses and businesses in that place and some are extremely big and expensive.
6. There is a booming business every summer, at the recreational area, where the Salt Lakes are located.
7. It is a small municipality and people know each other by name, which makes it home for the inhabitants

Despite, previous convincing evidence on the need to study place attachment in relation to DRR initiatives, there is scant literature, the varied findings on community attachment, and the lack of focus on place attachment suggest that it may be useful to design a research project to uncover the relationship between place attachment and flood preparedness. It will also be useful to examine the context of a developing country.

Research indicates that there are two elements that determine a community's or individual's attachment to a particular place, namely:

1. **Place dependency** occurs when the community rely on the environment because it has specific unique features or properties. Soltvyno features or properties include the salt domes, salt lakes, closeness to the border, budding tourism sector and acceptance of person with multiple ethnic origins (Schreyer, Jacob, & White, 1981).
2. **Place identity** occurs when a particular environ is used as a social network and emotions repository that provide a purpose and meaning to the lives of the particular community. Mishra et. al [38], life'' (Williams & Vaske, 2003, p. 831; Shamai, 1991).

According to Kiecolt and Nigg's (1982, p. 138), study on place attachment and earthquake evacuation, there are various factors that lead to community attachment, including:

1. land or house ownership;
2. a place that one considers a home whether owned, mortgaged or rented;
3. a feeling of belonging to one or more community groups;
4. the ratio of friends that live in the place; and
5. The duration that one has resided in the place.

Mazumdar & Mazumdar (2004), identified six factors that influence community attachment to a particular place, namely:

1. Narrative;
2. Economic – ties connected to places where someone can earn a livelihood;
3. Cosmology;
4. Genealogy – long-term ties developed from occupying a place for a long time, from one generation to another;
5. Pilgrimage; and
6. Religion – ties to a place where one can freely exercise their religion in a place of worship - dwelling.

Mishra et. al [38], compiled the economic, geological and religious components from the Mazumdar & Mazumdar (2004) study, to develop the place attachment scale.

4.3 The Household Survey Measures and Scales

4.3.1 Demographic Household Profile Scale

The Mishra et. al [38] demographic household survey contained the following nine variables:

1. Age;
2. Sex;
3. Family type;
4. Religion;
5. Caste;
6. Education;
7. Housing;
8. Annual income (in Rs.); and
9. Years of stay.

The caste variable was removed and annual income currency was changed from Indian rupees to United States Dollars (USD). In addition, we added other variables that are important for the case of Soltvyno, as indicated in Table 8.

Table 8. Demographic Household Profile Scale

Variables	Groups		
Age	Under 18	35-44	65-74
	18-24	45-54	75-84
	25-34	55-64	Other
Gender	Male		Female
Highest completed education	None	Vocational	Doctorate
	Basic / Primary	Bachelors	Post-doctorate
	Secondary	Masters	
Marital status	Single		Separated
	Married		Widowed
Highest completed education	None	Vocational	Doctorate
	Basic / Primary	Bachelors	Post-doctorate
	Secondary	Masters	
Marital status	Single		Separated
	Married		Widowed
Religion	Not sure	Protestantism	Hinduism
	Atheism	Judaism	Jehovah Witness
	Orthodox	Buddhism	Non-religious / unaffiliated
	Roman Catholicism	Paganism	Other
Ethnic origin	Ukrainian	Roma	Czech
	Rusyn or Ruthenians	Russian	German
	Hungarian	Slovak	Other, please specify
	Romanian		
Annual Income	Low (below \$1.90 a day)	Middle	High
Years of stay	Open (numerical)		
Housing type	Fully owned	Mortgaged	Other, please specify
	Rented		
Living situation	House alone	Nucleur Family	Extended Family
	House with partner	Joint Family	Other, please specify
Disability	Yes		No

The variable living situation, may be confusing and need further explanation. Nuclear family refers to the father, mother and children. The extended family comprises of the nuclear family together with other immediate relatives: grandparents, uncles, aunts, and cousins. The joint family is larger than the extended family, it is a multi-generational family. A family is referred to as a joint family if more than one generation live under one roof.

4.3.2 Place Attachment Scale

We modified the Mishra et. al [38] place attachment scale that contained 18 questions (Table 9). Respondents from Solotvyno were asked to indicate the extent to which they extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? Solotvyno is important to me because:

Table 9. Place Attachment Scale

Item	Measures
1. Being a border town, Solotvyno provides many opportunities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strongly disagree ▪ Disagree ▪ Neither agree nor disagree ▪ Agree ▪ Strongly agree
2. At this place, I have friends who can give me financial support.	
3. Here, I can get loans easily.	
4. I cannot think of a place other than this because I have fertile land here.	
5. The place provides me with livelihood opportunities that no other place can offer.	
6. Tourism business runs well here.	
7. The quality of salt in Solotvyno superior to other places.	
8. This is the only house that I have built.	
9. My forefathers and family lived and were buried in Solotvyno.	
10. Here, people know me by my house.	
11. My forefathers were very well-known persons in Solotvyno.	
12. I find the memory of my parents/grandparents in many parts of Solotvyno.	
13. My family members can work in the Czech Republic, Russia, Hungary and Ukrainian cities, and still continue to be residents of Solotvyno	
14. Due to my ethnic origin, I feel more at home in this place than any other part of Ukraine	
15. Being my ancestral place, I get all types of support here.	
16. I cannot feel contented without visiting my village church once a week.	
17. The collective festivals organized here like are very important to me.	
18. I like the diversity in local languages, schools and churches.	

The first seven questions of the place attachment scale address the economic dimension. The next questions (Q8 – Q15), address the genealogy dimension of the place attachment scale. The final three questions address the religious dimension of the place attachment scale.

4.3.3 Flood Preparedness Scale

The land subsidence preparedness scale was modified from the Mishra et. al [38] flood preparedness scale and the Mulilis Lippa Earthquake Preparedness Scale (Mulilis et al., 1990). The first part of the land subsidence scale focuses on the items that need to be in every household to ensure that they are prepared for the Solotvyno land subsidence risk (Table 10). The first land subsidence risk evaluation sub-scale seeks to answer the following two questions:

1. Do you have the following ready in case the land subsides? Please check to each item either 'yes', 'unsure' or 'no.'
2. Please rate the difficulty of preparing for each item, by your household, on a five-point scale ranging from 'not difficult at all' to 'extremely difficult.'

Table 10. First Land Subsidence Risk Evaluation Sub-Scale

Item	Are you prepared	Difficulty (1-5)
1. Important documents stored in a portable lockbox or safe-deposit box.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Yes ▪ No ▪ Unsure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Not difficult at all ▪ A little difficult ▪ Somewhat difficult ▪ Very difficult ▪ Extremely difficult
2. Home inventory stored in a portable lockbox or safe-deposit box.		
3. The radio is on and fully serviced.		
4. Torch lights / flashlights (with enough batteries) /candles / hurricane lamps / backup generator are ready.		
5. Emergency Supplies Kit that can serve as a “grab and go” bag		
6. Clean drinking water.		
7. First aid box.		
8. Necessary financial arrangements in case of a sudden evacuation.		
9. Insurance policy (property, health, life, and/or land subsidence)		
10. Emergency Response Communication Plan with a “family contact” outside Soltvyno?		

The second part of the land subsidence scale focuses on the community-based actions that each household should undertake to ensure that they are prepared for the Soltvyno land subsidence risk (Table 11). The second land subsidence sub-scale seeks to answer the following two questions:

1. Please indicate the extent of disaster risk preparedness by your household to each item, by checking either 'yes', 'unsure' or 'no.'
2. Please rate the difficulty of preparing for each item, by your household, on a five-point scale ranging from 'not difficult at all' to 'extremely difficult.'

Table 11. Second Land Subsidence Risk Evaluation Sub-Scale

Item	Are you prepared	Difficulty (1-5)
1. Do you know which government agency to contact when the land subsides?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Yes ▪ No ▪ Unsure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Not difficult at all ▪ A little difficult ▪ Somewhat difficult ▪ Very difficult ▪ Extremely difficult
2. Do you know the emergency warning signals and alert notifications used in Soltvyno?		
3. Do you participate in community discussions regarding land subsidence preparedness?		
4. Do you attend land subsidence preparedness meetings held by schools / NGOs / Municipality / Government?		
5. Have you familiarized yourself with the emergency plans of your family member's employment building, school, daycare center, or nursing home?		
6. Have you made the necessary property preparations to reduce the damage from land subsidence?		
7. Are you or someone in your family trained in first aid?		
8. Do you know how to prepare temporary shelter houses?		
9. Do you know which government agency to contact when the land subsides?		
10. Do you know the emergency warning signals and alert notifications used in Soltvyno?		

5 Risk Evaluation Approach

5.1 Risk Assessment Matrix

A risk assessment matrix is a chart that plots the severity of an event occurring on one axis, and the probability of it occurring on the other. You can also format the matrix as a table, where the risk likelihood and impact are columns, and the risks are listed in rows. By visualizing existing and potential risks in this way, you can assess their impact, and also identify which ones are highest-priority. From there, you can create a plan for responding to the risks that need the most attention.

A risk matrix chart is a simple snapshot of the information found in risk assessment forms, and is often part of the risk management process. These forms are more complex, and involve identifying risks, gathering background data, calculating their likelihood and severity, and outlining risk prevention and management strategies.

5.2 Risk Assessment Matrix Template

Also known as a “risk management matrix,” “risk rating matrix,” or “risk analysis matrix,” a risk assessment matrix (by any name) template focuses on two aspects:

1. **Severity:** The impact of a risk and the negative consequences that would result.
2. **Likelihood:** The probability of the risk occurring.

To place a risk in the risk assessment matrix, assign a rating to its severity and likelihood, then plot it in the appropriate position in your chart, or denote the rating in your table. The typical classifications used are: severity and likelihood.

5.3 Severity

Question 6.1 assesses the severity of the subsidence associated risks using the following parameters:

1. **Insignificant:** Risks that bring no real negative consequences, or pose no significant threat to the organization or project.
2. **Minor:** Risks that have a small potential for negative consequences, but will not significantly impact overall success.
3. **Moderate:** Risks that could potentially bring negative consequences, posing a moderate threat to the project or organization.
4. **Critical:** Risks with substantial negative consequences that will seriously impact the success of the organization or project.
5. **Catastrophic:** Risks with extreme negative consequences that could cause the entire project to fail or severely impact daily operations of the organization. These are the highest-priority risks to address.

5.4 Likelihood

Question 6.2 assesses the likelihood of the subsidence associated risks using the following parameters:

1. **Extremely Improbable:** Extremely rare risks, with almost no probability of occurring.
2. **Improbable:** Risks that are relatively uncommon, but have a small chance of manifesting.
3. **Remote:** Risks that are more typical, with about a 50/50 chance of taking place.
4. **Probable:** Risks that are highly likely to occur.
5. **Highly Probable:** Risks that are almost certain to manifest.

5.5 Classifying and Prioritising Risks

Risks that have severe negative consequences and are highly likely to occur receive the highest rank; risks with both low impact and low likelihood receive the lowest rank. Risk rankings combine impact and likelihood ratings to help identify which risks pose the greatest overall threats (and therefore are the top priority to address).

Some risk experts use a numeric scale to assign more specific risk rankings. However, most rankings fall into a few broad categories, which are often color-coded:

1. **Low:** The consequences of the risk are minor, and it is unlikely to occur. These types of risks are generally ignored, and often color-coded green.
2. **Medium:** Somewhat likely to occur, these risks come with slightly more serious consequences. If possible, take steps to prevent medium risks from occurring. They are not high-priority and should not significantly affect project success. These risks are often color-coded yellow.
3. **High:** These are serious risks that both have significant consequences, and are likely to occur. These risks should be prioritized and responded to as soon as possible. They are often color-coded orange.
4. **Extreme:** Catastrophic risks that have severe consequences and are highly likely to occur. Extreme risks are the highest priority. These risks require immediate response, as they threaten the success of the project. They are often color-coded red.

Once risks are ranked, a response plan should be made to prevent or address those that are “high” or “extreme.” You may not need to respond to risks ranked “low” or “medium” before work begins.

In the Solotvyno risk evaluation approach, we decided to get a clearer picture of risk by dividing the matrices into the following zones:

1. **Generally Acceptable (GA):** In the area of the chart ranked “low,” risks have little impact and/or are unlikely to occur. Risks in this region don’t pose an immediate threat to the project or organization, and some can even be ignored.
2. **As Low as Reasonably Possible (ALARP):** This is a zone of acceptable risk, encompassing the “low” and “medium” ranking areas. Risks falling within this region of the matrix are tolerable or not significantly damaging; work can proceed without addressing these risks being immediately.
3. **Generally Unacceptable (GU):** This is the area of the chart where risk is “high” or “extreme.” Risks in this region are quite damaging, highly likely to occur, and would threaten the project or organization. They are highest-priority, and you must address them immediately.

5.6 Validation and Risk Response

We were guided by three key documents, in the development of the risk evaluation approach:

1. [Smartsheet Risk Assessment Matrix](#);
2. International Standard IEC/ISO 31010 on Risk management — Risk assessment techniques [57]; and
3. EU general risk assessment methodology (Action 5 of Multi-Annual Action Plan for the surveillance of products in the EU (COM (2013)76) [58].

To ensure you've chosen the right risk matrix chart and completed it correctly, we validated it with a real-world scenario of Solutvyno municipality. Of course, a risk rating matrix is simply a tool to help guide decision-making. After collecting the data, we will carefully analyse both the matrices and the risks themselves before convening a Solutvyno DRR platform meeting to decide how to prevent, mitigate, or respond to a current or potential risk (Table 12).

Table 12. Generic REDA Risk Rating Matrix

RISK RATING KEY	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	EXTREME
	0	1	2	3
	ACCEPTABLE	ALARP (as low as reasonably practicable)	GENERALLY UNACCEPTABLE	INTOLERABLE
	OK TO PROCEED	TAKE MITIGATION EFFORTS	SEEK SUPPORT	PLACE EVENT ON HOLD
	SEVERITY			
	ACCEPTABLE LITTLE TO NO EFFECT ON EVENT	TOLERABLE EFFECTS ARE FELT, BUT NOT CRITICAL TO OUTCOME	UNDESIRABLE SERIOUS IMPACT TO THE COURSE OF ACTION AND OUTCOME	INTOLERABLE COULD RESULT IN DISASTER
LIKELIHOOD				
IMPROBABLE RISK IS UNLIKELY TO OCCUR	LOW - 1 -	MEDIUM - 4 -	MEDIUM - 6 -	HIGH - 10 -
POSSIBLE RISK WILL LIKELY OCCUR	LOW - 2 -	MEDIUM - 5 -	HIGH - 8 -	EXTREME - 11 -
PROBABLE RISK WILL OCCUR	MEDIUM - 3 -	HIGH - 7 -	HIGH - 9 -	EXTREME - 12 -

The risk assessment matrix template (Table 12) captures the essential information needed to gauge risks. It allows for each of the land subsidence each risk to be assessed, rated on its severity and likelihood, and finally plotted on a chart.

In more detail – Solutvyno Municipality DRR Household Survey (Annex D)

We have enclosed more detailed household survey questionnaire that details the risk evaluation approach for the case of Solutvyno.

6 Conclusion

Risk assessment and ranking is part of WP1 work, however, the task of WP3 is to conduct an evaluation of the risk assessment and incorporate the community values. Based on the community values and the evidence gathered under WP1, the risk rating matrix can be color-coded to visualize risk rankings and designate the GA, ALARP, and GU zones. This would enable the Solotvyno community at-a-glance to view which risks require to be prioritized.

The implementation of the risk evaluation approach is scheduled for September to end of November 2019. The developed household survey seeks to receive input from approximately 1000 to 2000 households. The risk evaluation approach will collect household survey data and contribute to the writing of a scientific paper on community-driven risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno. The final approach will collect information about the risk evaluation, the disaster risk preparedness and the place attachment. In addition, geo-referenced data will be collected to map the community perceptions on the land subsidence risk.

The results will be shared through the HumTechLab) and ImProDiReT community as part of the dissemination activities of these organizations. The final outcome of D3.3 will be a verified and locally adopted multi-stakeholder risk evaluation approach. In addition, the risk evaluation approach will be documented and (remotely) communicated to the local partners.

7 Definition of Terms and Principles

1. **Risk:** combination of the probability of occurrence of a hazard generating harm in a given scenario and the severity of that harm.
2. **Harm:** injury or damage to the health of people or damage to property, economic damage to consumers, damage to environment, security and other aspects defined in the scope of New Approach Directives.
3. **Hazard:** potential source of harm. The hazard, or danger, is intrinsic to the product.
4. **Probability of occurrence of that harm:** the likelihood of the harm occurring.
5. **Risk level:** Degree of risk, which may be 'serious', 'high', 'medium' or 'low'. When different levels of risks in different scenarios have been identified "the risk" of the product is given by the highest risk.
6. **Protection of Personal Data:** of both beneficiaries and humanitarian workers is often extremely important in order to safeguard their lives, dignity and privacy of both beneficiaries and humanitarian workers. This is contained in Article 8 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights which states: "1. Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her. 2. Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified. 3. Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority." The EU's Data Protection Directive (95/46/EC) also contain similar provisions, and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is also an important document with regard to personal data protection measures in the European Union.
7. **Safety and Security:** The term safety may be defined as a state in which an individual is free from physical and/or psychological harm and therefore, protected. Security are the steps or mechanisms put in place to achieve this state of protection (e.g., a safety barrier). These terms are inextricably linked as without security there is no safety.
8. **The principle of informed consent:** is also embedded in international legislation such as the GDPR and plays an important role in supporting privacy. When documenting information about serious human rights violations, unofficial investigators must strive to do no harm or to minimize the harm they may be inadvertently causing through their presence or mandate. This includes, gaining proper and informed consent from all victims and witnesses prior to being interviewed, externally examined, photographed, having their information recorded, being referred to any support services, or having their information and contact details shared with third parties. It is, therefore important to consider this principle carefully when introducing new technologies which often collect personal data and thus have privacy implications. However, this consideration may differ in times of crises. In fact, the collection of data may be of 'vital interest' in which case; the processing is necessary to protect someone's life. Or it may be a 'public task' in which the processing of data is necessary to perform a task in the public interest or for an official function, and the task or function has a clear basis in law. Thus, informed consent may not be necessary but what remains important is that the most appropriate lawful basis has been carefully considered, documented and applied.

Annexes

Annex A: ImProDiReT partners

Table 13. ImProDiReT Partners

ImProDiReT Partner	Short name	Country
1. Agency of the regional development of Zakarpattia	ARDZ	Ukraine
2. Institute of Geological Sciences of the National Academy of sciences of Ukraine	IGS NASU	Ukraine
3. Main School of Fire Service	MSFS	Poland
4. Delft University of Technology	TUD	The Netherlands
5. Resilience Advisory Network	RAN	United Kingdom

Annex B: Humanitarian IM Principles

HUMANITARIAN IM PRINCIPLES

Accessibility. Humanitarian information and data should be made accessible to all humanitarian actors by applying easy-to-use formats and by translating information into common or local languages when necessary. Information and data for humanitarian purposes should be made widely available through a variety of online and offline distribution channels including the media.

Inclusiveness. Multiple stakeholders, especially representatives of the affected population, should base information management and exchange on a system of collaboration, partnership and sharing with a high degree of participation and ownership.

Interoperability. All sharable data and information should be made available in formats that can be easily retrieved, shared and used by humanitarian organizations.

Accountability. Users must be able to evaluate the reliability and credibility of data and information by knowing its source. Information providers should be responsible to their partners and stakeholders for the content they publish and disseminate.

Verifiability. Information should be accurate, consistent and based on sound methodologies, validated by external sources, and analyzed within the proper contextual framework.

Relevance. Information should be practical, flexible, responsive, and driven by operational needs in support of decision-making throughout all phases of a crisis.

Impartiality. Information managers should consult a variety of sources when collecting and analyzing information to provide varied and balanced perspectives for addressing problems and recommending solutions.

Timeliness. Humanitarian information should be collected, analyzed and disseminated efficiently, and must be kept current.

Sustainability. Humanitarian information and data should be preserved, cataloged and archived, so that it can be retrieved for future use, such as for preparedness, analysis, lessons learned and evaluation. All stakeholders should promote the use of Open Source Software to further enhance access to information in a sustainable way. When possible, post-emergency data should be transitioned to relevant recovery actors and host governments and training provided on its use.

Humanity. Information should never be used to distort, to mislead or to cause harm to affected or at-risk populations and should respect the dignity of victims.

Reliability. Users must be able to evaluate the reliability and credibility of data and information by knowing its source and method of collection. Collection methods should adhere to global standards where they exist to support and reinforce credibility. Reliability is a prerequisite for ensuring validity and verifiability.

Reciprocity. Information exchange should be a beneficial two-way process between the affected communities and the humanitarian community, including affected governments.

Confidentiality. The processing of any personal data shall not be done without the prior explicit description of its purpose and will only be done for that purpose, and after prior informed consent of the individual concerned. Sufficient safeguards must be put in place to protect personal data against loss, unauthorized processing, and other misuse. If sensitive information is publicly disclosed, the sources of such information will not be released when there is a reasonable risk that doing so will affect the security or integrity of these sources.

Annex C: Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach (REDA)

1 Article

2 Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach (RED-A)

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9 **Abstract:** Research indicates that different contexts require different risk evaluation approaches.
10 There is limited research on the most feasible risk evaluation approach for a specific complex social-
11 technical context. Also, there is limited guidance on how to develop a methodology to identify the
12 best risk evaluation approach for a specific social-technical context. We develop the risk evaluation
13 decision-aiding approach (RED-A) that helps identify the best risk evaluation approach for a given
14 situation. We used the case of Sotolvyno to test the working of our developed approach. Sotolvyno
15 is a small village situated on the border of Ukraine that faces the risk of land subsidence due to the
16 flooding of the salt domes. In order to identify the most suitable approach, we reviewed multiple
17 existing approaches. After an intensive literature review, we arrived at four possible risk evaluation
18 approaches, namely: German Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU), the Th. Plattner
19 approach, The predictive, Bayesian risk classification scheme (PBRC Scheme) and the Pollard
20 approach. We made comparisons between the different approaches. After analysing each approach,
21 we concluded that the two approaches: WBGU and PBRC, are the most suitable in the case of
22 Sotolvyno. The case study shows that the RED-A works and is useful. Future research will entail
23 applying one of the recommended approaches in Sotolvyno municipality and assessing the
24 feasibility of the decision-aiding methodology to select a viable risk evaluation approach.

25 **Keywords:** Risk Evaluation Approach; Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR); Risk Governance; Complex
26 Socio-technical System; Decision-aiding Methodology; Land Subsidence; Sotolvyno municipality;
27 Community-based risk assessment; Tolerability and Acceptability Judgment; Risk Evaluation
28 Criteria.

30 1. Introduction

31 There are many different definitions of risk by researchers from diverse disciplines. By some, it
32 is the likelihood of occurrence of an event [1], for others, it is the consequences of an event [1, 2] while
33 others combine the two elements [3]. Other researchers define risk as uncertainty about the
34 occurrence of an event and the damage that might be incurred [4]. Various researchers propose one
35 common definition that entails both the likelihood of occurrence of an event and its possible
36 consequences [1, 4]. By combining these descriptions, we define risk as the likelihood of an event
37 occurring and the severity of its consequences. To clarify this definition, we provide two examples,
38 as follows:

- 39 1. The likelihood of dying because of a plane crash is so low that it is almost pointless to quantify.
40 However, the consequences in terms of loss of life, economic losses coupled with the
41 environmental impacts, are extremely large; hence, it is still perceived as a risk.
- 42 2. The likelihood of a child falling during their first bicycle ride is high; however, the consequence
43 is may not be severe. In this case, it is also perceived as a risk because the likelihood is high.

44 A person may decide to accept the risk of dying in a plane, or a child may decide to accept the
45 risk of falling during their first bicycle ride. These decisions are known as risk-taking decisions. Risk

46 evaluation is known as the process of deciding whether to accept, tolerate or avoid a risk. In this
 47 paper, we define risk evaluation as making judgments regarding the tolerability and acceptability of
 48 a particular risk, depending on whether risk reduction measures are needed.

49 Risk evaluation is the third phase in risk governance [3]. The four phases of risk governance are
 50 pre-assessment, risk-appraisal, risk evaluation and risk management. Figure 1 visualizes this process.
 51 The main goal of risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and the acceptability of a given risk,
 52 based on the scientific evidence collected in the risk appraisal phase and societal values [3, 5-7].
 53 Tolerability refers to a willingness to live with a particular risk as long as taking the risk is worth it
 54 and the risk is adequately controlled [8]. Acceptability only occurs when there is no need to take risk
 55 reduction measures to ensure safety [9]. Risk reduction measures only apply to tolerable risks.
 56 Acceptable risks do not require risk reduction measures. In the case of intolerable risks, the risk
 57 reduction measures outweigh the benefits of tolerating the specific risk.
 58

59

60 Figure 1. IRGC Risk Governance Framework. Source: Risk Governance Towards an Integrative
 61 Approach (Source: Ortwin Renn, 2005).

62 Risk evaluation takes place after risk appraisal and before risk management. Risk appraisal
 63 contains two sub-phases: risk assessment and concern assessment. At the risk assessment sub-phase
 64 the identification, describing, mapping and analysing of each hazard takes place according to its
 65 likelihood of occurrence and its consequences should a disaster occur. Afterwards, we assessed
 66 exposure and vulnerability and estimated whether the risk is high, moderate or low [6]. Analysing
 67 vulnerability takes place during the concern assessment sub-phase and entails risk perceptions, social
 68 concerns and socio-economic impacts. Thus, the risk appraisal phase gathers evidence on the hazard
 69 (risk assessment), exposure (risk assessment) and vulnerability (concern assessment).

70 Risk evaluation is a sub-phase of the tolerability and acceptability judgement phase and occurs
 71 before risk characterisation. In categorisation the creating of risk profiles take place, judgments on
 72 the seriousness of risk are made, and risk reduction options are taken into consideration. After the
 73 judgement of tolerability and acceptability, risk management takes place. Tolerability and
 74 acceptability judgments are critical in deciding whether there is a need for risk reduction measures.

75 Research indicates that individual risk-taking decisions are dependent on the nature of the risk
 76 and the societal context [10-14]. A person may choose to avoid, accept, transfer, mitigate or exploit a
 77 risk, based on the likelihood and consequences of the risk and their social context [12]. Kaspersen
 78 [10] explain that the context a person is in affects their decision and preferences. Müller and Rau [12],
 79 conclude that the social context, the societal preferences and the level of heterogeneity of a particular

80 risk affects the individual decision whether or not to take the risk. This research demonstrates that
81 “people’s choices are not only context-dependent but are sensitive to their degree of inequality
82 aversion” [12], (p. 116). Li and Yu [11] explain context-dependent choice using the foraging theory to
83 explain the persistence of choice behaviour and provide insights regarding “unchosen alternatives”
84 [11], (p. 170). Therefore, choosing a specific risk evaluation approach for a particular social context
85 may be better than using the same approach in any context.

86 Furthermore, in some social contexts determining the likelihood and consequences of a
87 particular risk is highly uncertain. These social contexts are known as complex socio-technical
88 systems. Onencan [15], (p. 1) explains that “socio-technical systems emphasise social (actors,
89 networks, organisations) and technical systems, in the design, analysis and systems operation.”
90 According to Sheard [16] complex systems

91 “do not have a centralising authority and are not designed from a known specification, but
92 instead involve disparate stakeholders creating systems that are functional for other purposes
93 and are only brought together in the complex system because the individual “agents” of the
94 system see such cooperation as being beneficial for them.”

95 The main question that we seek to answer in this paper is: “How do you develop a methodology
96 to identify the best risk evaluation approach for a specific social-technical context?”. To answer the
97 research question, we developed an approach to identify the best risk evaluation approach for
98 Solotvyno. Due to the different existing approaches, there must also be a method that guides DRR-
99 experts in choosing one. The purpose of this paper is to design this method.

100 In order to find a suitable risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno, we analysed multiple existing
101 approaches and selected four possible risk evaluation approaches that matched our definition. These
102 four approaches are the approach by the German Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU), the
103 Th. Plattner approach, The predictive, Bayesian risk classification scheme (PBRC scheme) approach
104 and the Pollard approach [5, 17-19]. The four approaches were compared based on various criteria,
105 and two approaches: WBGU and the PBRC Scheme were found to be most suitable for Solotvyno
106 municipality. The results are useful for direct application, in the case of Solotvyno, regarding the
107 subsidence risk. However, the methodology can also be used by researchers to identify the most
108 feasible risk evaluation approach for a particular socio-technical context.

109 This paper is structured as follows. Section two presents the analytical framework. After that,
110 the method of the literature review and the literature review process. Section 4 contains the results,
111 including the strengths and weaknesses of the different approaches. Section 5 contains the case study
112 of Solotvyno. Finally section 5 discusses the RED-A, the application of the RED-A, limitations and
113 future research.

114 **2. Towards a Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Criteria**

115 The goal of risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and the acceptability of a given risk [5]. To
116 determine which approach is most applicable for a given socio-technical context, the different
117 approaches must be assessed to decide whether they aid in reaching the primary goal for the
118 evaluation for that particular context. Most DRR experts use a criterion to determine the tolerability
119 and acceptability of a risk [20-22]. Those criteria are useful for defining the exact format of the
120 parameters used for decision making [23]. Use of criteria is preferred by DRR experts who seek clarity
121 and structure to present the results and their analysis. For this paper, we selected to use the risk
122 acceptance criteria to present the results, including the comparisons between the different
123 approaches.

124 *2.1. Existing Risk Evaluation Criterion*

125 To be able to assess the approaches with the use of risk acceptance criteria, firstly the existing risk
126 acceptance criteria will be explained. Various researchers came up with risk evaluation criteria that,
127 according to their research, should be included in an approach in order to correctly evaluate risk. In
128 the following paragraphs, the risk evaluation criteria of 3 researchers will be explained.

129 2.1.1 *The Health and Safety Executive criterion (HSE criterion)*

130 The HSE is an organisation with the mission to prevent work-related death, injury and ill health.
131 HSE's roots stretch back to 1833 and with expertise in risk assessment. The Health and Safety
132 Executive (HSE) [24] propose three criteria for determining the tolerability and the acceptability of a
133 given risk: the equity-based criterion, the utility-based criterion, and the technology-based criterion.

134 The equity-based criterion starts the premise that all individuals have a right to minimal
135 protection. The criterion can be implemented by establishing a maximum limit above which no
136 individual can be exposed in order to ensure minimal individual safety.

137 The utility-based criterion regards to the trade-off between the costs and benefits of taking
138 measures to reduce risk. It is the process of determining if the benefits resulting from the measures
139 are worth the required investment. According to French et al. (2005, Ref. 15), the costs linked to a risk
140 can be divided in three parts, i.e. (i) the costs linked to safety (implementation of risk reduction
141 measures); (ii) the costs linked to the impacts of the risk on the workers (professional diseases and
142 accidents); and (iii) the costs linked to the consequences of the risk to the public.

143 The technology-based criterion indicates if there is already a way to reach acceptable or tolerable
144 risk through the use of practices such as standards and professional practice. The danger of this
145 criterion is the fact that it can lead to ignoring the costs related to using those standards and practices.
146

147 2.1.2 *Vrijling, Hengel and Houben criterion*

148 J.K. Vrijling, W. van Hengel and R.J. Houben are three engineers from the faculty of civil
149 engineering, which is a faculty of the Technical University of Delft. Research done by J.K. Vrijling,
150 W. van Hengel and R.J. Houben [25] revealed that there are two points of views in studies of the
151 acceptability of risk. The first point of view is that an individual weighs risk against direct and
152 indirect personal benefits. In other words, the decision to accept risk has a cost/benefit character. This
153 point of view leads to the personally acceptable level of risk with this proposed definition by Vrijling
154 et al. [25]: "The frequency at which an individual may be expected to sustain a given level of harm
155 from the realisation of specified hazards." The second point of view is the degree of voluntariness
156 with which the decision is taken, and the degree of risk endured. Although the societal decision-
157 making process weighs the social benefits against social costs, including risk, this process of appraisal
158 is not easily made explicit.

159 2.1.3 *Kasperson criterion*

160 Roger E. Kasperson is an American risk analyst, research Professor and a Distinguished Scientist.
161 In the research called acceptability of human risk, Roger E. Kasperson states that the following five
162 contexts or comparisons are paramount for judging risk acceptability: the risk as compared with
163 natural background, the risk compared with other risks prevalent in society, the risk in the context of
164 the magnitude of associated benefits, the costs of risk reduction, and the risks of available substitutes
165 [9]. The risk as compared with natural background suggests an increment to risk afforded by
166 performing a specific activity. The second comparison is the risk compared with other risks prevalent
167 in society. For example the comparison between risks previously determined to be tolerable by a
168 particular risk guardian. The third context that Kasperson mentions is the risk in the context of the
169 magnitude of associated benefits. Together with the fourth context of the costs of risk reduction, this
170 is seen as a trade-off between costs and benefits. The final analysis involves the examination of risks
171 of available substitutes. Actions designed to reduce risks sometimes create new and perhaps more
172 considerable risks.
173

174 2.2 *The Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Criteria*

175 To arrive at an extensive set of criteria, we included all three of the studies above. After compiling all
176 the criterion from the three studies, we ended up with a total of 9 risk acceptance criteria. We have

177 merged the corresponding criteria to create a clear structure. Figure 2 shows which criterion are
 178 merged.

179
 180 **Figure 1.** Merging of the criteria
 181

182 We identified nine elements combined into three criteria. The aim is not to find the approach
 183 that includes the most elements, but the approach that includes all the most critical elements for a
 184 specific socio-technical context. In section 5 we will explain this further with the help of a case study.
 185

186 **3. Materials and Methods**

187 In this method section, we have extensively described the steps we took to develop the
 188 methodology, the choices we made and the rationale. This study used a systematic literature review
 189 in order to investigate past research that developed a qualitative risk evaluation approach. It was
 190 decided to focus on non-mathematical approaches so that the research did not become too extensive
 191 and we were able to finish it in the given time. During a systematic literature review, it is imperative
 192 to stay critical and focused because not all sources and articles are reliable [26].

193 We first looked up and compared different definitions of risk. Then we derived a set of keywords
 194 that we chose to use as consistent search terms when searching all resources [26]. The search terms
 195 we have used are: risk (A1), risk definition (A2), risk probability (A3), risk consequence (A4), define
 196 risk (A5) and what is a risk (A6).

197 After defining risk, we needed to explain the risk governance framework, so we searched for
 198 risk articles that included a detailed explanation of this process. We decided to use one of the articles
 199 that we already found during our search for definitions of risk.

200 In order to compare different community-based risk evaluation approaches, we had to find the
 201 existing approaches. We used a third set of search terms to find articles on community-based risk
 202 evaluation approaches. This last set consists of the search terms: risk evaluation approaches (B1),
 203 community-based risk evaluation (B2), community-based risk evaluation approaches (B3), risk
 204 evaluation methods (B4) and criteria for evaluating risk (B5). To narrow down the publications, We
 205 have combined those terms with disaster, hazard or natural hazard.

206 In order to find studies about the risk, we have used five different electronic databases, namely:

- 207 1. Google Scholar
- 208 2. Scopus
- 209 3. ScienceDirect
- 210 4. SpringerLink
- 211 5. JSTOR.

212

213 We used those databases because all of them contain a lot of scientific papers that can be of great
 214 value to our research. Table 1 summarises all the strategies used for finding evaluation approaches
 215 and the outcome.

216

Table 1. Search strategies for evaluation approaches.

Keywords	Databases	Search outcome	Last date of search
	Google Scholar	1010	01/05/2019
	ScienceDirect	190	
("risk evaluation approaches" OR "community-based risk evaluation" OR "community-based risk evaluation approaches" OR "risk evaluation methods" OR "criteria for evaluating risk") AND ("disaster" OR "natural hazards" OR "hazards")	SpringerLink	177	
	Scopus	74	
	JSTOR	5	

217

218 In total, we obtained 1456 publications from searching for electronic databases. To filter the right
 219 articles from the first set of publications, a selection was made based on the title of the publications.
 220 We looked at whether the title was related to the research subject.

221 Establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria for study participants is a standard, required
 222 practice when designing high-quality research protocols [27]. Table 2 presents the inclusion and
 223 exclusion criteria used for this systematic review. There was no restriction applied to the date of
 224 studies sampled, and we searched all databases for studies published up to 01/05/2019.

225

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications must be peer-reviewed • Publications that describe risk evaluation and not risk analysis or risk identification • Publications that describe a specific usable approach
Exclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications that describe a part of risk assessment that is too specific • Publications that are not written in Dutch or in English • Publications that are only available as abstract

226

227 To make sure the articles are valid and reliable, we restricted the search to peer-reviewed articles.
 228 Furthermore, because we are researching risk evaluation approaches, the approaches must be risk
 229 evaluation approaches and not risk assessment approaches. To assess whether an approach was for
 230 risk evaluation, we checked whether the approach considered the evidence only or evidence and
 231 values. We also eliminated the publications that were not Dutch or English and the articles that we
 232 could not access the full copy while scanning the titles. Abstract only articles were excluded because
 233 we needed a detailed explanation of the different approaches.

234 After this step, the number of relevant publications reduced from 1456 to 40. We then read the
 235 abstract of all 40 articles, and on that basis, we selected the relevant articles. After reading all the
 236 abstracts and eliminating unsuitable publications based on the exclusion criteria, we arrived at only
 237 12 articles. Because 12 articles are relatively few, we decided to use the snowballing method.

238 We started with backward snowballing, which means identifying relevant publications from the
 239 reference list of the most relevant publication that passed the quality assessment step. When we
 240 finished backward snowballing, we applied forward snowballing [28]. Forward snowballing implies
 241 checking the publications that cite publications that are considered relevant and passed the
 242 assessment step. All the papers that we found through snowballing underwent the same assessment
 243 step, as mentioned earlier in the section.

244 After the snowballing, we had 23 articles found via the search terms and four articles extra that
 245 we came across during the research. Those remaining articles' full texts were read to arrive at the
 246 final selection. Figure 2 is a visualisation of the selection process.

247

248

Figure 2. Article selection flow chart

249 Some of the publications we found include a risk evaluation approach. We also searched for
 250 requirements for an effective risk evaluation approach. Therefore, we searched for publications that
 251 included criteria that are used for determining the tolerability and the acceptability of risk. Using the
 252 search term “risk acceptance criteria,” we found three relevant and peer-reviewed articles.

253 In sub-section 2.2, we selected nine sub-criteria to use for determining the tolerability and the
 254 acceptability of risk comprising of 3 main criteria.

255 After that, we analysed whether each of the nine elements were included in the different risk
 256 evaluation approaches. Those elements are placed in the rows of table 6, and the approaches are the
 257 columns. When we concluded that an approach takes an element into account, we placed a
 258 checkmark in the row of that element.

259

260 4. Results

261 4.1 Risk evaluation approaches

262 In this section we explain the found approaches in detail. All criteria will be checked and
 263 explained to enable a good comparison of the approaches.

264

Table 3. Risk evaluation approaches

Approach	Main factors	Reference
WBGU	Nine criteria: Extent of damage, Probability of occurrence, Extent of damage, Incertitude, Ubiquity, Persistency, Reversibility, Delay effect, Violation of equity, Potential of mobilisation	Klinke and Renn [5]
Th. Plattner approach	Six criteria: Voluntariness, Reducibility, Knowledge, Endangerment, Extent of damage, Frequency of event	Plattner [19]
PBRC Scheme	Nine characteristics: Potential consequences, Uncertainty about consequences, Ubiquity, Persistency, Delay effect, Reversibility, Violation of equity, Potential of mobilisation and the difficulty in establishing appropriate performance measures.	Kristensen, Aven [17]
Pollard approach	Seventeen criteria: Stock at Risk, Knock-on Effects, Spatial Extent, Heterogeneity, Spatial Extent, Sensitivity of Receptor, Severity of Effect, Temporal Extent, Latency, Accumulation, Reversibility, Scarcity, Notoriety, Unfairness, Imposition, Distrust.	Pollard, Davidson [18]

265

266 Table 3 shows the risk evaluation approaches that we encountered during the literature review.
 267 All the approaches make use of a variety of criterion to evaluate a given risk. These approaches can
 268 be considered as risk evaluation approaches because they do contain de societal aspects as well as
 269 the technical aspects of risk.

270

271 4.2 Selected Risk Evaluation Approaches

272 First, we will briefly explain the approaches that were found during the literature review to gain
 273 a better understanding of all the approaches and their purposes. For each approach, the risk
 274 evaluation criterion will be explained.
 275

276 4.2.1 WBGU approach

277 Klinke and Renn decided that they wanted to include more criteria than the classic components
 278 such as the extent of damage and the probability of occurrence. To find more criteria they looked into
 279 the researches of Boholm in 1998, Sjöberg in 1999, Slovic in 1987 and 1992 and Rohrman & Renn in
 280 2000. The result was a long list of criteria that was not identical for different groups. The WBGU had
 281 addressed this problem by involving many experts in finding the most suitable criteria. These criteria
 282 ended up to be: the extent of damage, probability of occurrence, the extent of damage, uncertainty,
 283 ubiquity, persistency, reversibility, delay effect, violation of equity and potential of mobilisation.

284 The extent of damage is about the adverse effects in, for example, the number of deaths or the
 285 number of injured. The probability of occurrence is an estimate for the relative frequency of a discrete
 286 or continuous loss function. Uncertainty is the umbrella term for all uncertain components. Ubiquity
 287 indicates the degree of the geographical spread of potential damages and persistency indicates the
 288 degree of temporal spread of potential damages. By reversibility we mean the possibility to restore
 289 the situation to the state before the damage occurred. The delay effect describes the delay between
 290 the activity and the actual impact of that activity. Violation of equity is about the discrepancy between
 291 those who enjoy the benefits and those who bear the risks.

292 Klinke and Renn decided to divide the potential of mobilisation criteria into four major elements:

- 293 1. Inequity and injustice associated with the distribution of risks and benefits over time, space, and
 294 social status (thus covering the criterion of equity).
- 295 2. Psychological stress and discomfort associated with the risk or the risk source (as measured by
 296 psychometric scales).
- 297 3. Potential for social conflict and mobilisation (degree of political or public pressure on risk
 298 regulatory agencies).
- 299 4. Spill-over effects that are likely to be expected when highly symbolic losses have repercussions
 300 on other fields such as financial markets or loss of credibility in management institutions.
 301

302 4.2.2 Th. Plattner approach

303 In his research, Plattner suggests that evaluation criteria can be used to compute the perceived
 304 individual risk and acceptable individual risk. The factors he found focuses on natural hazard risk
 305 perception on the individual level. We compiled the list of factors The list of factors based on the
 306 literature on risk perception. The factors found were then presented to a group of experts who
 307 selected the most relevant factors. The factors found are as follows: voluntariness, reducibility,
 308 knowledge, endangerment, the extent of damage and frequency of the event. Some of those factors
 309 have a slightly more extensive meaning; Table 5 shows what each factor represents.

310 **Table 4.** Th. Plattner evaluation criteria

Evaluation criteria	Represents
Voluntariness:	Voluntariness
Reducibility:	Reducibility, Predictability, Avoidability
Knowledge:	Familiarity,

	Knowledge about risk, Manageability
Endangerment:	Controllability, Number of people affected, Fatality of consequences, Distribution of victims, Scope of area affected, Immediacy of effects, Directness of impact
Extent of damage:	Extent of damage
Frequency of event:	Frequency of event

311

312 *4.2.3 PBRC Scheme*

313 Kristensen and Aven criticised the WBGU approach of Klinke and Renn. Their main point of
314 critique was related to the understanding and meaning of what risk is. Kristensen and Aven present
315 a Bayesian risk classification schema based on the WBGU schema, which they believe therefore is
316 considered as a modified version of the WBGU schema. The PBRC schema consists of nine
317 characteristics. Some of the characteristics are taken directly from the WBGU schema, some are
318 modified, and some are new. The nine proposed characteristics are potential consequences,
319 uncertainty about consequences, ubiquity, persistency, delay effect, reversibility, violation of equity,
320 the potential of mobilisation and the difficulty in establishing appropriate performance measures.
321 We will only discuss the modified and new characteristics in detail, for the other character see section
322 3.2.1. The two characteristics: potential consequences and uncertainty about consequences are the
323 two key characteristics, while the other seven characteristics are used to describe aspects of these two
324 characteristics. The potential consequence is indicated with observable quantities like the number of
325 fatalities or the number of injuries. Factors such as variability in humans, animals, plants and
326 technical systems; systematic and random measurement errors within the data used as background
327 information; indeterminacy resulting from a genuine stochastic relationship between cause and
328 effects etc. should all be taken into consideration when assessing the uncertainty about consequences.
329 A new characteristic that Kristensen and Aven included is the difficulty in establishing appropriate
330 performance measures. This characteristic is included in order to represent this aspect of risk
331 assessment. They recommend qualitatively describing this characteristic so the experts can give their
332 opinion about the appropriateness of the selected quantities or measures on a scale from, for example, 0
333 to 10.

334

335 *4.2.4 Pollard approach*

336 The Pollard approach consists of 17 attributes that are classified according to those characterising the
337 physical properties of the harm and those characterising the social response or valuation of the harm.
338 We will briefly explain each of those attributes:

339

340

Table 5. Explanations of the Pollard attributes

Attribute	Explanation
Stock at Risk	Represents a valuation of the overall harm, either in economic terms or in terms of numbers of receptors.
Knock-on Effects	

	Reflects that harm to one receptor may affect the wellbeing of another receptor.
Spatial Extent	Denotes the overall area in which exposures to the hazard that causes environmental harm are experienced.
Heterogeneity	Reflects that within the overall area denoted by Spatial Extent, there may be heterogeneity in exposure to the hazard.
Sensitivity of Receptor	Reflects the proportion of receptors exposed that exhibit the harm.
Severity of Effect	Defines the general physical effect on an individual sensitive receptor only.
Temporal Extent	Denotes the length of time that the environmental harm will be experienced.
Latency	The period of time before the consequent environmental harm starts to be realized during the hazard.
Accumulation	The changes in rate at which the harm progresses over time.
Reversibility	Considers both whether the effects of the harm are reversible and, if so, over what time scale.
Scarcity	Reflects the abundance of the receptor, and is used to consider the loss of cultural resources, as well as physical environments.
Dread	Reflects that society can have an aversion to, or fear of, a harm that may be largely unrelated to its physical nature.
Unfamiliarity	Gives an assessment of concern that may arise out of a low degree of knowledge and understanding of the harm.
Notoriety	Reflects the potential for raised awareness of, and anxiety about, the harm via the media and other channels and information.
Unfairness	Reflects the discontent that may arise from the inequity or unfairness of a harm's distribution.
Imposition	Measures the social value afforded by the degree of personal control over the harm.
Distrust	

Captures the consequences of a lack of trust in the characterisation of the harm or in those responsible for its management.

341

342 In order to see which approach scores on which criteria, we formulated an element for each of
 343 the criterion mentioned above. We ended up with the following set of elements: Does the approach
 344 include/take into account?

- 345 1. the cost/benefit character? (U1)
 346 2. the costs related to risk reduction? (U2)
 347 3. the magnitude of associated benefits? (U3)
 348 4. a criterion specifically focused on not passing a maximum? (E1)
 349 5. a criterion that compares the risk with other risks prevalent in society? (E2)
 350 6. a criterion that takes the degree of voluntariness to account? (E3)
 351 7. a criterion that compares the risk with the risk level during the natural background? (T1)
 352 8. a criterion that focuses on existing solutions? (T2)
 353 9. a criterion that also looks at the risks of available substitutes? (T3)
 354

355

Table 6. Results of Applying the Risk Evaluation Methodology

Approaches	WBGU	Th. Plattner approach	PBRC Scheme	Pollard approach
Utility-based criterion	U1	✓		✓
	U2	✓	✓	✓
	U3	✓		✓
Equity-based criterion	E1	✓		✓
	E2		✓	✓
	E3	✓	✓	✓
Technology-based criterion	T1		✓	
	T2	✓	✓	
	T3			

356

357 Table 6 gives a structured and organised way of which elements each approach includes. The
 358 WBGU approach and the PBRC Schema contain the most elements. The Th. Plattner approach focuses
 359 more on the equity-based criterion and the technology-based criterion and does not cover the utility-
 360 based criterion. The Pollard approach does not contain any element of the technology-based criterion
 361 but scores good on the utility-based criterion and the equity-based criterion.

362

5. Case study

363 In this paper we use a case study to demonstrate the developed RED-A. We chose to use a case
 364 study because “the knowledge accumulates not around the original case but around the potentially
 365 more generic phenomena that was discovered or explained in the original case study” [29]. This
 366 means that we can not only find out if the method works for Soltvyno but for other contexts as well.

367

5.1 Introduction to Soltvyno

368 Soltvyno municipality, which is the selected case study in this paper, qualifies as a complex
 369 socio-technical context because of the following qualities:

370 We selected Soltvyno because of her specific socio-technical situation. It is a small village
 371 situated in the Tyachev district of the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine that faces the risk of land
 372 subsidence due to the flooding of the salt domes. It is located close to the border with Romania, on
 373 the right bank of the Tisza River. The Carpathian sea deposited kilometres of high-quality salt many
 374 mega-annums ago [30]. Since the 1790s, salt has been mined in this area [31]. This process remained
 375 uninterrupted because there was clay protecting the upper part of the salt-dome [32]. To enable salt
 376 mining in the upper part of the salt-dome, the mining company removed the protective layer. In 1908

377 water began to filtrate the galleries, thereby dissolving the salt leading to flooding in the salt-mines
378 [30]. This led to the formation of Lake Cunegunda [31]. The mines flooded and the water slowly
379 moved into the cavities, dissolving the salt and the land slowly subsided. As a result of the eroded
380 rock salt domes the ground subsided, and in some parts collapsed, leading to deformation of several
381 houses [31]. Looking at those consequences, it becomes clear that the salt mining has created certain
382 risks. Because of this risk, risk evaluation is needed to judge the acceptability and tolerability.

383 One key challenge facing disaster risk reduction (DRR) is decision science neither provides
384 guidance nor a universally accepted methodology to select a suitable risk evaluation approach, for a
385 particular complex socio-technical system [33]. While we know that different social-technical contexts
386 need different risk evaluation approaches, it is difficult for DRR experts to choose between various
387 existing methods. Also, though various risk evaluation approaches exist, very few have been tried
388 and tested in various complex socio-technical contexts.

389 The absence of a single, empirically verified and universally accepted methodology for selecting
390 the appropriate risk evaluation approach for a select complex socio-technical context, is a significant
391 challenge. The existing risk evaluation approaches have fundamental differences in terms

392 The main goal of this paper is to design a methodology for selecting the most suitable evaluation
393 approach for a given complex socio-technical context. The selected complex socio-technical context
394 is situated risk governance of Soltvyno municipality.

395 The aim is not to find the approach that includes the most elements, but the approach that
396 includes all the most critical elements for Soltvyno municipality. That is why it is crucial that we
397 first explain how unique Soltvyno is and why it is necessary to look for a specific approach.

398 *5.1 Uniqueness of Soltvyno and the Risk Evaluation Criteria*

399 Every case has its own set of essential elements that should be included in the risk evaluation
400 approach [12]. Hence, the risk is created by various actors who sometimes benefit from this risk while
401 other people living in Soltvyno bear the risks. The fact that people benefiting are benefitting from
402 the risk makes the case more complex, and that is why it requires a particular approach. When an
403 actor concludes that it is more beneficial to take the risk, he accepts the risks and tries to manage it
404 instead of mitigating it [34].

405 The criteria of costs related to risk reduction is vital for Soltvyno as well. There was less
406 allocation of money to manage water in the mine when the Russian government was no longer
407 managing the mines [30]. Even more important are the costs of filling the created holes, reclaiming
408 the land and removing the objects that have remained of the mining shafts. Therefore, the costs
409 related to risk reduction do have a significant impact on the risk level in Soltvyno.

410 The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits is also particularly relevant for
411 the Soltvyno case. is due to approximately the same reason as with the first element, namely the fact
412 that some people benefit from the cause of the risk.

413 The degree of voluntariness element also has to be considered because some inhabitants
414 accepted the risk by continuing to either live or conduct business in the high-risk zones. Even though
415 the inhabitants are free to move wherever they want, their options are limited if they cannot find a
416 job, a suitable school or place of worship, in the new place, so they choose to stay in Soltvyno. Mishra
417 et al. [35] created a place attachment scale, which consists of 18 items to assess the level that a person
418 is attached to a specific place [35]. This elements in the scale explain various reasons why the
419 Soltvyno inhabitants could choose to stay[35]. By the place attachment scale, literature review and
420 the interviews conducted in Soltvyno, the inhabitants of Soltvyno feel attached to the place, due
421 to:

- 422 1. The inhabitants are of mixed origin, and Soltvyno is the only place that they do not feel the
423 pressure to integrate. The municipality governance structure has taken account of the
424 complexity of its inhabitants and supported the emergence of nationality-based schools,
425 multiple religious places and
- 426 2. The main burial site is on a hill where most of the inhabitant's forefathers are buried, and they
427 need proximity to the place to visit their deceased loved ones regularly and later would like to

- 428 be buried next to their forefathers. Relocation would reduce the chances of being buried with
 429 their family, and they cannot move with their deceased loved ones.
- 430 3. Its proximity to the Romanian-Ukrainian border, which provides a livelihood to some of them
 431 through cross-border trade.
- 432 4. The inhabitants have friends and relatives living there who provide emotional and financial
 433 support.
- 434 5. The inhabitant's own houses and businesses in that place and some are extremely big and
 435 expensive.
- 436 6. There is a booming business every summer, at the recreational area, where the Salt Lakes are
 437 located.
- 438 7. It is a small municipality and people know each other by name, which makes it home for the
 439 inhabitants.
- 440 The place attachment indicators show that most of the current Solotvyno inhabitants prefer not
 441 to leave their current environment [36]. Because there may be cases where individuals and groups
 442 accept the risk when serious risk reduction measures have to be taken, this risk is a problem.

443 5.2 Most suitable approach for Solotvyno

444 To find out which approach is most applicable to the Solotvyno case, we must analyze the
 445 approaches on their strengths and weaknesses, and then the best fit for the Solotvyno must be
 446 determined. The analysis of the approaches has already been done in section 4.

447 In section 5.1, we explained the uniqueness of Solotvyno by the importance of a few of the
 448 elements. These were the following elements: The cost/benefit character, The costs of risk reduction,
 449 The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits, Degree of voluntariness and Existing
 450 solutions. In order to pick the best approach for the Solotvyno case, we must look at which approach
 451 contains most of these elements.

452 **Table 8.**

Approaches	WBGU	Th. Plattner approach	PBRC Scheme	Pollard approach
The cost/benefit character	✓		✓	✓
The cost of risk reduction	✓	✓	✓	✓
The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits	✓		✓	
Degree of voluntariness	✓	✓	✓	✓
Existing solutions	✓	✓	✓	

454 Table 8 shows that two approaches meet all the requirement of a sound risk evaluation approach
 455 for Solotvyno. These are the WBGU approach and the PBRC scheme approach. Because the PBRC
 456 Scheme contains one extra element that is considered essential for effective risk evaluation, we
 457 conclude that the PBRC Schema is the most suitable approach for Solotvyno.

458 During our research, we encountered a few striking findings. We will explain all the findings,
 459 the assumptions and limitations and the suggested future research in the discussion section.
 460

461

462 **6. Discussion**

463 There are various different risk evaluation approaches that are all suitable for different kind of
 464 situations [5, 17-19]. To be able to select an approach it is important to first gain knowledge about the
 465 situation where risk evaluation must be carried out. In this paper we used the case of Soltvyno to
 466 test our developed RED-A. In this discussion we will focus on a detailed explanation of our method
 467 first, than we will discuss the application on Soltvyno and we conclude with limitations of the
 468 research.

469 **6.1 RED-A**

470 Little guidance can be found about how to choose between different existing risk evaluation
 471 approaches. Because one approach can be much more suitable for a situation than another approach,
 472 finding a decision-aiding approach is very useful. The question we sought to answer in this paper is
 473 therefore: "How do you develop a methodology to identify the best risk evaluation approach for a
 474 specific social technical context?". During this research we developed the RED-A, that acts as
 475 guidance on how to select a suitable risk evaluation approach for a specific case. We tested our
 476 method on the unique case of Soltvyno and came to the conclusion that the RED-A can support a
 477 lot of guidance in choosing a risk evaluation approach. The RED-A contains 4 steps, namely: literature
 478 review, selecting priority criteria, risk evaluation criteria and ranking risk evaluation approaches. To
 479 give a better understanding of the process we provided a visualization in figure 3.

480

481

Figure 3

482 First a literature review has to be performed. By defining a set of search terms that describe the
 483 wanted risk evaluation approaches, a systematic search for articles including risk evaluation
 484 approaches can be conducted. When the useful articles are selected based on the inclusion and
 485 exclusion criteria, the risk evaluation articles have to be separated from the risk assessment articles.
 486 It must therefore be considered here whether the focus is on acceptability and tolerability and not on
 487 identification or estimation. With too few found articles, the snowballing method can be used. Then
 488 again, the risk evaluation articles have to be distinguished from the risk assessment articles. The last
 489 step of the literature review is picking the actual approaches from the articles and describing them in
 490 detail. An extensive explanation is needed for a good analyzation in the last step.

491 The next step is selecting the specific priority criteria for the chosen case study. In order to do so
 492 the risk assessment report and the concern assessment report have to be analyzed. After the
 493 analyzation the current situation has to be compared with the reports. The contradictions between
 494 the reality and the reports have to be identified and explained further with information found during
 495 a subsequent literature review. Place attachment also plays an important role in selecting priority
 496 criteria and therefore has to be reviewed. Finally the current situation has to be compared with the 9
 497 risk evaluation criteria to compile a list of priority criteria for the case study.

498 The aforementioned risk evaluation criteria are established by combining multiple risk
 499 evaluation criteria into groups. The more general risk evaluation criteria of HSE have been chosen as
 500 grouping criteria. Although the criteria from Vrijling et al. [25] and Kasperson [9] are only about risk
 501 acceptability, we considered them as useful because they were grouped into the HSE criteria and
 502 those do take tolerability into account. The criteria that are grouped under the utility-based criterion
 503 are all focused on either costs or benefits or both of them. Under the equity-based criterion we
 504 grouped the elements with the emphasis on the rights and feelings of individuals. The third criteria
 505 about technology includes elements regarding to existing solutions and any new related risks.

506 At last the found approaches have to be ranked based on how many priority criteria they
 507 include. All evaluation criteria must be checked for each approach. As guidance on how to decide
 508 whether an approach includes an element we composed a checklist. For this checklist, see figure 4.

An approach includes **the cost/benefit character** when it incorporates:

- Costs (money, deaths or injured) and benefits (money or jobs).
- Violation of equity (people are enjoying benefits while others are bearing the risk).

An approach includes **the costs of risk reduction** when it incorporates:

- Costs related to proposed risk reduction measures.
- "How much society wishes to spend to avoid a particular consequence."¹

An approach includes **the risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits** when it incorporates:

- A comparison of risk and benefits.
- A determination of how much risk reduction should be undertaken.

An approach includes **a maximal limit that cannot be crossed** when it incorporates:

- "The premise that all individuals have unconditional rights to certain levels of protection"².
- "A limit to present the maximum level of risk above which no individual can be exposed"².

An approach includes **the risk compared with other risks prevalent in society** when it incorporates:

- Comparisons with risk previously determined to be tolerable.
- Comparisons with similar risk reduction technologies.

An approach includes **degree of voluntariness** when it incorporates:

- "Whether an activity is acceptable in terms of the risk involved for the total population"³.
- Undermining the possibility of voluntary risk taking.

An approach includes **the risk as compared with natural background** when it incorporates:

- A comparison that suggests the increment to risk afforded by an activity.
- Analyses of the increase in risk.

An approach includes **existing solutions** when it incorporates:

- The reviewing of existing solutions.
- The results of other studies about risk evaluation.

An approach includes **the risk of available substitutes** when it incorporates:

- The checking of the actions designed to reduce risks for possible bigger risks.
- The consideration that risk is likely to accrue from increased use of substitutes.

509
510

Figure 4. Checklist

511 Figure 4 is a check list as guidance on how to decide if an approach includes an element. If one
512 of the two boxes is ticked, than automatically it qualifies.

513 *6.2 Application of RED-A to Solotvyno*

514 As described above, we started with a literature review to select risk evaluation approaches that
515 work with criteria. We ended up with 4 risk evaluation approaches: the WBGU, the Th. Plattner
516 approach, the PBRC Schema and the Pollard approach. Thereafter we conducted a study on
517 Solotvyno to be able to select the priority criteria. The risk in Solotvyno is a consequence of the mining
518 of salt. It becomes clear from that, that there are costs and benefits associated with this risk.
519 Furthermore there are various costs associated with reducing this risk. Removing all residents is not
520 a very suitable option because people are attached to their place of residence and because these
521 people cannot get jobs in other places just like that. Based on this information, we have selected 5
522 priority criteria for the case of Solotvyno, which are as follows: the cost/benefit character, the cost of
523 risk reduction, the risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits, degree of voluntariness
524 and existing solutions. During the selection of priority criteria we also searched for risk evaluation
525 criteria prepared by experts. These two steps are carried out in parallel because the formulation of
526 the risk priority criteria and the risk evaluation criteria must correspond in order to draw a
527 conclusion. We found 9 risk evaluation criteria which experts believe are necessary for a good
528 approach [9, 24, 25]. Subsequently we carried out the final step, starting with analyzing the four
529 approaches. By going trough the checklist given in figure 4 it can be found out which approach
530 contains which elements. Then it must be counted which approach contains the most priority criteria.
531 The risk evaluation approach that contains the most priority criteria can be considered most suitable
532 for the case. In our case the two approaches: WBGU and PBRC schema both include all the priority
533 criteria. To reach a conclusion, non-priority criteria can be considered. The PBRC schema contains
534 one extra element of comparing the risk with the risk level during the background. If there are enough
535 resources to implement this element, this approach can be seen as the best because it includes all the
536 priority criteria and one extra risk evaluation element relative to the WBGU approach.

537 *6.3 Complexity*

538 First of all, the complexity of the social context in Solotvyno. As we already mentioned, the case
539 of Solotvyno is unique, and therefore needs a specific risk evaluation approach. It is a place with a
540 deep-rooted culture, many different nationalities and beliefs [37]. Apart from the Ukrainians,
541 Solotvyno is the home for a lot of other nations such as Hungarians, Romanians, Roma, Slovaks,
542 Germans, Russians and more of the former Union of Soviet Socialist Republics [37]. As a result, there
543 are a lot of different cultures, norms and values. In finding a suitable risk evaluation approach, all
544 these different groups must feel heard.

545 The risk in Solotvyno is caused by the mining of salt, which at the time brought benefits for some
546 of the residents and risk for others [36]. This makes this case more unique and more complex. Not all
547 residents wanted the same thing, and even now, not everyone agrees with each other about what
548 should happen with the salt domes in the future [38, 39].

549 Because it is a unique and complex situation, a specific approach had that met Solotvyno's
550 requirements had to be found. In the analytical framework, we have described what the necessities
551 are for a suitable risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno. This information allowed us to pick the best
552 approach for this specific case.

553 *6.4 Separating risk evaluation approaches from risk appraisal approaches*

554 Although the risk appraisal phase and the tolerability and acceptability judgement phases are
555 two different phases in the framework, the terms are often used incorrectly. While looking for risk
556 evaluation approaches, we have often come across risk appraisal approaches. The search terms we
557 used are only about evaluation, and they do not mention risk appraisal. We selected all the articles
558 with approaches that were labeled risk evaluation approaches and ended up with quite a few articles.

559 However, after thoroughly studying the articles, we found out that most of the approaches we found
560 with these terms were about risk appraisal. The term risk evaluation is often used incorrectly to
561 indicate risk appraisal methods. The goal of risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and
562 acceptability of a given risk. Risk appraisal entails assessing the identification and estimation of
563 hazards. The use of wrong terms made searching for risk evaluation methods more complex. More
564 than once we incorporated a risk appraisal method in our research by mistake, which we eliminated
565 when we concluded that it was not a real risk evaluation approach. For well executed research with
566 risk evaluation approaches as the main subject, there must be the certainty that it is actually about
567 risk evaluation and not about risk appraisal. To be sure of this, every approach was checked several
568 times to see if it was about acceptability and tolerability, and not about assessing risk.

569 *6.5 Assumptions and limitations*

570 The four-risk evaluation approaches we picked are criteria-based methods. To decide whether
571 an approach met an element, we read the criteria with their explanations, if there was an explanation.
572 However, none of the articles explained the criteria in great detail. As a result, it was difficult to
573 estimate whether certain elements are included in an approach.

574 It was a limitation to arrive at the best risk evaluation because there is no full information about
575 each approach. Because not every criterion was explained in detail, assumptions had to be made
576 about if an approach did include an element or not. We applied the same assumptions to all
577 approaches so that the assessment would be fair.

578 **Supplementary Materials:** The following are available online at www.mdpi.com/xxx/s1, Figure S1: title, Table
579 S1: title, Video S1: title.

580 **Author Contributions:** For research articles with several authors, a short paragraph specifying their individual
581 contributions must be provided. The following statements should be used “conceptualization, X.X. and Y.Y.;
582 methodology, X.X.; software, X.X.; validation, X.X., Y.Y. and Z.Z.; formal analysis, X.X.; investigation, X.X.;
583 resources, X.X.; data curation, X.X.; writing—original draft preparation, X.X.; writing—review and editing, X.X.;
584 visualization, X.X.; supervision, X.X.; project administration, X.X.; funding acquisition, Y.Y.”, please turn to the
585 [CRediT taxonomy](#) for the term explanation. Authorship must be limited to those who have contributed
586 substantially to the work reported.

587 **Funding:** Please add: “This research received no external funding” or “This research was funded by NAME OF
588 FUNDER, grant number XXX” and “The APC was funded by XXX”. Check carefully that the details given are
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592 contribution or funding sections. This may include administrative and technical support, or donations in kind
593 (e.g., materials used for experiments).

594 **Conflicts of Interest:** Declare conflicts of interest or state “The authors declare no conflict of interest.” Authors
595 must identify and declare any personal circumstances or interest that may be perceived as inappropriately
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597 of the study; in the collection, analyses or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the
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599 no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the
600 manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results”.

601 **Appendix A**

602 The appendix is an optional section that can contain details and data supplemental to the main
603 text. For example, explanations of experimental details that would disrupt the flow of the main text,
604 but nonetheless remain crucial to understanding and reproducing the research shown; figures of
605 replicates for experiments of which representative data is shown in the main text can be added here
606 if brief, or as Supplementary data. Mathematical proofs of results not central to the paper can be
607 added as an appendix.
608

609 Appendix B

610 All appendix sections must be cited in the main text. In the appendixes, Figures, Tables, etc.
611 should be labelled starting with 'A', e.g., Figure A1, Figure A2, etc.
612

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Annex D: Community-based Risk Evaluation Approach (CREA) Survey

ImProDiReT Risk Evaluation Approach for Soltvyno Municipality

English

Informed Consent Form

Q1.1. Name of school

- Romanian Secondary School of Soltvyno
- Ukrainian Secondary School of Soltvyno
- Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Soltvyno
- Romanian Lyceum of Soltvyno

Q1.2. Name of student / teacher

Q1.3. Type of participant

- Teacher
- Student's Household
- Neighbour 1
- Neighbour 2

Q1.4.

Before agreeing to participate in the study, it is important that you read the following explanation. After reading the explanation of the study (informed consent form), please, answer the following questions by ticking either the "Yes" or "No" boxes

Title and details of research: Risk Evaluation Approach for the Soltvyno Municipality. This study is part of the larger European Union project "Improving Disaster Risk Reduction in the Transcarpathia Region", Ukraine - ImProDiReT (Principal Investigator (henceforth "PI"): Prof. Bartel Van de Walle, EU DG ECHO project 783232 on Risk Governance). More information on this project can be found here: <http://www.improdiret.eu/>

Researcher: Dr. Abby Muricho Onencan (henceforth "Researcher"), Department of Multi-Actor Systems, Section Policy Analysis, Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management, Delft University of Technology, NL

Purpose of the research: The purpose of the survey is to assess how we can make the Soltvyno community safe. The data will provide input for the community action plan to reduce risks associated to the collapse of the land near the salt mines.

Confidentiality and data management: We will collect information about the risk evaluation, the disaster risk preparedness and the place attachment. In addition, geo-referenced data will be collected to map the community perceptions on the land subsidence risk. Processing and storing of your data will be handled in accordance with the European Union 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation. You have the right to request access to, change or erasure of your personal data at any time. Any personal sensitive data, such as names, identities, location, will be replaced, scrambled or blurred to ensure that anonymized data cannot be linked back to you. The anonymized data may be used for research and publications. For the project duration (September 1 2019 - February 29, 2020), personal information will only be accessible to the project members (the Researcher a PI). The data are stored in the Netherlands and are never made available to third parties. After the project, the anonymized data and research results (non-personal) will be archived for a period of 10 years and will be accessible to anyone.

Explanation of procedures: You will be invited to answer a set of questions about your perceptions of the land subsidence risk in Soltvyno municipality, your level of preparedness and how attached you are to the area. The estimated duration to answer the questions ranges from 15 - 30 minutes.

Risks: The main risks of participating in the study are linked to the interception of your personal data during the processing and storage of the information provided by you to complete this study. The researcher has minimized the risks by using only the anonymized data that cannot be linked back to you and taking the appropriate measures of storage and access control to secure the sensitive data during and after the project. The data interception risks are thus minimal. Participation in the survey is otherwise safe for the participants. By participating in this study, you do not undergo specific health risks.

Questions: Any questions concerning the research and the survey and/or in the case of issues due to the research can be directed to the researcher, Abby M. Onencan, TU Delft /Faculty of TPM, Jaffalaan 5, 2628 BX Delft, Email: A.M.Onencan@tudelft.nl.

Yes No

1. I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked were answered to my satisfaction.

	Yes	No
2. I voluntarily consent to be a participant in this study. I understand that I can refuse to answer questions and I can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. I understand that taking part in the study involves the risk of the interception of my personal data during the processing and storage of the information provided by me to complete this study. I furthermore understand that the researcher has minimized the risks by taking the appropriate measures of storage and access control to secure the sensitive data during and after the project.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. I understand that the anonymized information (anonymized survey transcript) I provide will be used for publications and other research-related activities (e.g., reports, website, blogs, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me, where I live, will not be shared beyond the researcher and the PI.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q1.5. Signature

SIGN
HERE

clear

Demographics

Q2.1. Age

- | | |
|--------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Under 18 | <input type="radio"/> 55-64 |
| <input type="radio"/> 18-24 | <input type="radio"/> 65-74 |
| <input type="radio"/> 25-34 | <input type="radio"/> 75-84 |
| <input type="radio"/> 35-44 | <input type="radio"/> Other |
| <input type="radio"/> 45-54 | |

Q2.2. Gender

- Male
- Female

Q2.3. Highest completed education

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> None | <input type="radio"/> Bachelors |
| <input type="radio"/> Basic / Primary | <input type="radio"/> Masters |
| <input type="radio"/> Secondary | <input type="radio"/> Doctorate |
| <input type="radio"/> Vocational | <input type="radio"/> Post-doctorate |

Q2.4. Marital status

- | | |
|-------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Single | <input type="radio"/> Separated |
| <input type="radio"/> Married | <input type="radio"/> Widowed |

Q2.5. Religion

- | | |
|--------------------------------|--------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Not sure | <input type="radio"/> Buddhism |
| <input type="radio"/> Atheism | <input type="radio"/> Paganism |
| <input type="radio"/> Orthodox | <input type="radio"/> Hinduism |

- Roman Catholicism
- Protestantism
- Judaism

- Jehovah Witness
 - Non-religious / unaffiliated
 - Other
-

Q2.6. Ethnic origin

- Ukrainian
- Rusyn or Ruthenians
- Hungarian
- Romanian
- Roma

- Russian
 - Slovak
 - Czech
 - German
 - Other, please specify
-

Q2.7. Annual Income

- Low (below \$1.90 a day)
- Middle

- High

Q2.8. Home address (Name of street)

Q2.9. Based on the zoning in the map (below), please indicate which area you reside, work, your children go to school, you go to church, conduct business, or rent apartments (houses). Only indicate the areas that apply to your circumstance.

	Reside	Work	Children go to school	Attend church	Have a business	Regularly frequent the area	Rent apartments / house (s)
1. Magura Mountain Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>					
2. Terrace Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>					
3. Mine 9 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>					
4. Mine 8 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>					
5. Mine 7 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>					
4. Salt Lake area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>					
6. Blackmoor area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>					

Household

Q3.1. How many years have you lived in Solotvyno?

Q3.2. What is your housing type?

- Fully owned
- Rented
- Mortgaged
- Other, please specify

Q3.3. What is your household size?

Q3.4. What is your family type?

- Nuclear
- Extended
- Single parent
- Childless
- Other, please specify

Q3.5. What is your living situation?

- House alone
- House with partner
- Nucleur Family
- Joint Family
- Extended Family
- Other, please specify

Q3.6. Does any member of your household have a disability (mobility, visual, hearing, cognitive)?

- Yes
- No

Place Attachment Scale

Q4.1. Please indicate, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? Solotvyno is important to me because:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. Being a border town, Solotvyno provides many opportunities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. At this place, I have friends who can give me financial support.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Here, I can get loans easily.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. I cannot think of a place other than this because I have fertile land here.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. The place provides me with livelihood opportunities that no other place can offer.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
6. Tourism business runs well here.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. The quality of salt in Sotolvyno superior to other places.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. This is the only house that I have built.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. My forefathers and family lived and were buried in Sotolvyno.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10. Here, people know me by my house.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
11. My forefathers were very well known persons in Sotolvyno.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
12. I find the memory of my parents/grandparents in many parts of Sotolvyno.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
13. My family members can work in the Czech Republic, Russia, Hungary and Ukrainian cities, and still continue to be residents of Sotolvyno	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
14. Due to my ethnic origin, I feel more at home in this place than any other part of Ukraine	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
15. I cannot feel contented without visiting my village church once a week.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
16. The collective festivals organized here like are very important to me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
17. I like the diversity in local languages, schools and churches.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
18. Being my ancestral place, I get all types of support here.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Land Subsidence Preparedness Scale

Q5.1. Do you have the following ready in case the land subsidizes? Please check to each item either 'yes', 'unsure' or 'no.'

	Yes	Unsure	No
1. Important documents stored in a portable lockbox or safe-deposit box.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Home inventory stored it in a portable lockbox or safe-deposit box.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. The radio is on and fully serviced.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Torch lights / flashlights (with enough batteries) /candles / hurricane lamps / backup generator are ready.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Emergency Supplies Kit that can serve as a "grab and go" bag	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Clean drinking water.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. First aid box.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. Necessary financial arrangements in case of a sudden evacuation.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. Insurance policy (property, health, life, and/or land subsidence)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10. Emergency Response Communication Plan with a "family contact" outside Sotolvyno?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q5.2. Please rate the difficulty of preparing for each item, by your household, on a five-point scale ranging from 'not difficult at all' to 'extremely difficult.'

	Not difficult at all	A little difficult	Somewhat difficult	Very difficult	Extremely difficult
1. Important documents stored in a portable lockbox or safe-deposit box.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. Home inventory stored it in a portable lockbox or safe-deposit box.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. The radio is on and fully serviced.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Torch/flashlights (with enough batteries) /candles/ hurricane lamps / backup generator are ready.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Emergency Supplies Kit that can serve as a "grab and go" bag	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Clean drinking water.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. First aid box.	<input type="radio"/>				
8. Necessary financial arrangements in case of a sudden evacuation.	<input type="radio"/>				
9. Insurance policy (property, health, life, and/or land subsidence)	<input type="radio"/>				
10. Emergency Response Communication Plan with a "family contact" outside Sotolvyno?	<input type="radio"/>				

Q5.3. Please indicate the extent of disaster risk preparedness by your household to each item, by checking either 'yes', 'unsure' or 'no.'

	Yes	Unsure	No
1. Do you know which government agency to contact when the land subsidizes?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Do you know the emergency warning signals and alert notifications used in Sotolvyno?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Do you participate in community discussions regarding land subsidence preparedness?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Yes	Unsure	No
4. Do you attend land subsidence preparedness meetings held by schools / NGOs / Municipality / Government ?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Have you familiarized yourself with the emergency plans of your family member's employment building, school, daycare centre, or nursing home?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Have you made the necessary property preparations to reduce the damage from land subsidence?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. Are you or someone in your family trained in first aid?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. Do you know how to prepare temporary shelter houses?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q5.4. Please rate the difficulty of preparing for each item, by your household, on a five-point scale ranging from 'not difficult at all' to 'extremely difficult.'

	Not difficult at all	A little difficult	Somewhat difficult	Very difficult	Extremely difficult
1. Do you know which government agency (local, regional or central) to contact when you face land subsidence problems?	<input type="radio"/>				
2. Do you know the emergency warning signals and alert notifications used in Sotolvyno?	<input type="radio"/>				
3. Do you participate in community discussions regarding land subsidence preparedness?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Do you attend meetings held by schools / NGOs / Municipality / Government to improve land subsidence preparedness?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Have you familiarized yourself with the emergency plans of your family member's employment building, school, daycare centre, or nursing home?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Have you made the necessary property preparations to reduce the damage from land subsidence?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Are you or someone in your family trained in first aid?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. Do you know how to prepare temporary shelter houses?	<input type="radio"/>				

Sotolvyno Community-based Risk Evaluation

Q6.1. In your opinion, what is the level of danger for people living or conduct business(es) in the following areas? (refer to the Q2.8 map)

	CATASTROPHIC (Immediate relocation)	CRITICAL (Very dangerous, living there is not recommended)	MODERATE (need for risk reduction measures to reduce the risks)	MINOR (risky only in specific places that can be avoided or cured)	INSIGNIFICANT (generally safe)
1. Magura Mountain Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Terrace Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Mine 9 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Mine 8 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Mine 7 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Salt Lake area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Black moor area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q6.2. In your opinion, what is the likelihood/probability that the following subsidence related consequences will occur if the current situation continues unchecked?

	Highly Probable	Probable	Remote	Improbable	Extremely Improbable
1. Loss of Life / Lives	<input type="radio"/>				
2. Severe casualties (locals and tourists).	<input type="radio"/>				
3. Economic loss (damaged/collapsed buildings & infrastructure).	<input type="radio"/>				
4. No drinking water (destruction of water facility)	<input type="radio"/>				
5. No schools (Hungarian, Romanian etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Salination of agricultural grounds	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Salination of Tisza and Danube Rivers (downstream)	<input type="radio"/>				
8. Loss of work	<input type="radio"/>				
9. Homelessness	<input type="radio"/>				
10. No transport infrastructure (destruction of rail and main roads)	<input type="radio"/>				
11. No cooking gas (destruction of the gas pipeline)	<input type="radio"/>				
12. Backout in Sotolvyno (long-term) and Rakiv region (destruction of the electric power substation)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q6.3. Suppose you have been given ownership to a house in any of the areas below, based on your current understanding of the land subsidence risk in Solotvyno, what would you choose? For each item, please select either '**Option A**' (accept ownership and move in immediately), '**Option B**' (only accept ownership if certain safety measures are implemented first), or '**Option C**' (decline to reside in the area)

	Accept ownership and move in immediately	Only accept ownership if certain safety measures are implemented first	Decline to reside in the area
1. Magura Mountain Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Terrace Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Mine 9 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Mine 8 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Mine 7 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Salt Lake area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Black moor area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q6.4. Suppose you have been given business license to construct your tourist resort in any of the areas below, based on your current understanding of the land subsidence risk in Solotvyno, what would you choose? For each item, please select either '**Option A**' (accept the license and construct the resort immediately), '**Option B**' (only accept the license if certain safety measures are implemented first), or '**Option C**' (decline to conduct any business in the area)

	Accept the license and construct the resort immediately	Only accept the licence if certain safety measures are implemented first	Decline to conduct business in the area
1. Magura Mountain Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Terrace Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Mine 9 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Mine 8 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Mine 7 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Salt Lake area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Black moor area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q6.5. Suppose you have been given license to mine salt and construct a speleotherapy hospital in any of the areas below, based on your current understanding of the land subsidence risk in Solotvyno, what would you choose? For each item, please select either '**Option A**' (accept the license and start mining and construction immediately), '**Option B**' (only accept the license if certain safety measures are implemented first), or '**Option C**' (decline to conduct any business in the area)

	Accept the license and start mining and construction immediately	Only accept the licence if certain safety measures are implemented first	Decline to conduct business in the area
1. Magura Mountain Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Terrace Slopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Mine 9 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Mine 8 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Mine 7 area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Salt Lake area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Black moor area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q6.6. What would you prefer to be **DONE** to resolve the subsidence problem? For each item, please select either '**Option A**' (prefer 100% implementation), '**Option B**' (prefer implementation to acceptable levels), or '**Option C**' (prefer no change to current situation).

	100% implementation	Implementation to acceptable levels	No change of current situation
1. Clean the salt lakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Strengthen the retaining wall systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Speedup liquidation of the salt mining company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Implement an early flood warning system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Restore critical infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Conserve old mining industrial archaeology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. Develop a drinking water network for the salt lakes zone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. Develop a sludge line system for the salt lakes zone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. Divert and update the sewer system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10. Fill the sinkholes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	100% implementation	Implementation to acceptable levels	No change of current situation
11. Clean-up all the salt lakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
12. Cap old boreholes and shafts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
13. Strict application of building codes and construction laws	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
14. Establish and fence off exclusion zones	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
15. Reclaim land in the exclusion zones	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
16. Identify relocation zones in or near Soltvyno	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
17. Relocate inhabitants living near Black Moor	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
18. Relocate inhabitants living in other high-risk zones	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
19. Remove mine shafts and other objects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
20. Demolish old and unsafe mining infrastructure above the surface	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
21. Demolish unsafe buildings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
22. Demolish unsafe infrastructures	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q6.7. What would you prefer to be **STOPPED** to resolve the subsidence problem? For each item, please select either '**Option A**' (prefer 100% implementation), '**Option B**' (prefer implementation to acceptable levels), or '**Option C**' (prefer no change to current situation)

	100% stopped	stopped only to acceptable levels	No change to current situation
1. Stop underground flooding in the mines	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Stop leakage of water pipelines	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Stop leakage from sewage pipelines near Mine 8	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Stop issuance of salt mining business licenses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Stop issuance of recreation business licenses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Stop future plans for shaft (underground) salt mining	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. Stop future plans for salt solution (open) salt mining	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. Stop exploitation of the Soltvyno mine and surrounding area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. Stop exploitation of the recreation (Salt Lake) area	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10. Stop pumping brine from abandoned mines into salt pools	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
11. Stop the use of salt resources (brine and rock salt) for health purposes (hospital: speleotherapy)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
12. Stop further construction in the Salt Lake zone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
13. Stop the pollution of the salt lakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
14. Stop exploitation of alluvium in the Tisza River floodplain	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
15. Stop digging boreholes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
16. Stop unregulated disposal of waste near collapses and sinkholes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Final Reflection

Q7.1. In your opinion, can the Soltvyno land be restored/rehabilitated/ cured?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe, please explain

Q7.2. Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. We truly value the information you have provided. Your responses will help us identify the most effective solutions that may ensure that Soltvyno is safe. Please check for the report on the on www.improdiret.eu, which will be available early 2020. If you have any comments on the survey or the project, please leave a comment below.

Annex E: Household Survey TOR for the Teachers

Monthly Translation and Progress Report Writing Services Terms of reference

Project	Improving Disaster Risk Reduction in Transcarpathia, Ukraine (2018 – 2020)
Period	3 months (with a possibility to extend for another 2/3 months)
Type / Position	Monthly Translation and Progress Report Writing Services for the Risk Evaluation Approach Implementation by Soltvyno Teachers (Monthly Translation and Progress Report Writing Services into Soltvyno local languages of 400 Euros per teacher)
Activation lead	Abby Muricho Onencan – a.m.onencan@tudelft.nl
Support team	Kenny Meesters and Bartel Van de Walle
More information	Improdiret.eu

1. Background

In furtherance of the SENDAI framework, the ImProDiReT project started in March 2018 with a lifetime of 24 months with the financial support of the European Union Civil Protection Mechanism. The project aim is to improve risk governance within the Transcarpathian Communities in Ukraine, with a particular focus on the Soltvyno village. In the first project year, ImProDiReT has collected risk assessment geodata for the larger Transcarpathia region and Soltvyno municipality in Ukraine. The geodata was collected for a variety of purposes, such as creating models, automatically generating PDF reports, and for integration in web-based applications to evaluate risks and support decision-making. To supplement the geodata, there is need for an evaluation of community perceptions and their level of preparedness and attachment to Soltvyno.

The most challenging phase in the risk management process is risk evaluation. It involves the delineation and justification of judgments on the acceptability and tolerability of certain risks. When a risk is tolerable, additional risk reduction actions need to be undertaken as opposed to acceptable risks where no risk reduction effort is required

because the risks are considered to be very low. The difficult task is drawing a line between what is considered 'intolerable,' and 'tolerable' and between 'tolerable' and acceptable.'

Current risk approaches rely on two inputs, namely evidence, and values. Renn (2008), explains that values are an essential part of risk evaluation because "what the society is supposed to tolerate or accept can never be derived from looking at the evidence alone (p. 37) [1]." Hence we have frameworks developed such as the SENDAI framework, which affirm that communities play an essential role in Disaster Risk Reduction decision-making processes [2].

This assignment will inform and partly contribute to ImProDiReT project deliverable 3.3 on developing a community-based risk evaluation approach for the Soltvyno Saltmine case study. The assignment of the school teachers in the four main schools in Soltvyno (minus the boarding school) is centered around the collection of household survey data to support the developed risk evaluation approach and also contribute to the writing of a scientific paper on community-driven risk evaluation approach for Soltvyno. The task will include assigning tasks to teachers and students to collect the household survey data, coordinating the collection of the data, motivating and providing guidance to the students in the data collection process, explaining the parts in the questionnaire that may not be clear to some of the Soltvyno household, collating the data and forwarding it to TUD and writing a short reflection report. The results will be shared through the HumTechLab) and ImProDiReT community as part of the dissemination activities of these organizations.

2. The Planned Process

According to the 2016 population census, Soltvyno has a population of 8,791 people. However, after face to face discussions with a number of Soltvyno inhabitants, it is believed that the number has significantly reduced after the closing of the mines. Many of the young people and men have left the municipality in search of jobs elsewhere. The actual population is not known. The numbers also vary depending on the season, with the summer season having the highest peak due to the booming tourist market. Therefore, the risk evaluation survey will target only a percentage of the population.

The process first begun by developing a draft risk evaluation approach. Then four teachers were selected to represent the four main schools.

According to the Soltvyno schooling system, the primary and secondary and high school in one place – and they are all called secondary school. The various classes are grouped into primary, basic secondary education and high education. The classes are broken down as follows:

- Class 1 – 4 is primary (6-10 years)
- Class 5 – 9 is basic secondary education (11 – 15 years)
- Class 10 – 11 is high education – secondary (16 -17 years)

There is no University, Institutes or Vocational Schools in Solotvyno.

Therefore, the four schools that will be targeted are:

- Romanian Secondary School of Solotvyno
- Ukrainian Secondary School of Solotvyno
- Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Solotvyno
- Romanian Lyceum of Solotvyno

The Solotvyno Boarding school was eliminated from the list of target schools because the families of the students are not from Solotvyno. The school consists of pupils from neighboring villages, which is not the focus of the household survey. In addition, boarding students are restricted from leaving the school compound to conduct household surveys.

The lead teachers for every school will be the English teachers, apart from the Romanian Lyceum where we will work with the Head teacher. The English teachers were selected to ease communications and coordination exercises between TUD and the four schools.

The risk evaluation questionnaires will be answered by:

1. All the teachers in the school.
2. The family member of each student between the ages 11-17 years (1 questionnaire per household). Please note that for siblings, only one household questionnaire will be filled for their household. However, each sibling will be encouraged to reach out to different neighbors and encourage them to fill the questionnaires.
3. Neighbors of the students (one young family and one elderly family or if not possible any two neighbors). Teachers should encourage the students to select their respondents from diverse groups (age, gender, family setup, religion...)

Table 1 provides the information regarding the number and ages of the students who will be engaged, the number of teachers expected to fill the questionnaires and coordinate students to collect the data, and details regarding the four main teachers who will represent the four schools in the risk evaluation household data collection process (**Romanian school data will be filled later**).

Schools in Solotvyno	Grade	6-10 yrs	11-15 yrs	16-17 yrs	# pupils	# Qs (x3)	# of teachers	# total Qs	Contact person
Hungarian	1st to 11th	73	63	19	82	246	19	265	Viktoria Andyush
Ukrainian / Russian	1st to 11th	214	237	34	271	813	34	847	Tyagunova Natalia
Romanian School	1st to 11th				0	0	35	35	Tsipile Olga
Romanian Lyceon	8th to 11th		24	30	54	162		162	Popp Adriana
TOTAL						1221	88	1309	

After the household survey is concluded, TUD will prepare small souvenirs with the project name for all the teachers and students. Depending on the available budget, TUD will select one or two possible souvenirs from the following proposed list:

1. Bag
2. Pencil case
3. Pen
4. Calendar / Note Book
5. Cup

To motivate the schools, each souvenir will be printed with the name of the school, as follows:

- Romanian Secondary School of Solotvyno
- Ukrainian Secondary School of Solotvyno
- Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Solotvyno
- Romanian Lyceum of Solotvyno

3. The Planned Outputs

Each teacher will be expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Contribution to the ImProDiReT project deliverable 3.3: Risk evaluation approach through supporting the collection of household survey data on the approved risk evaluation approach;
- The collected data will contribute to the development of a scientific paper on community-centered risk evaluation approaches, with the exact topic to be defined after data is collected; and
- Prepare a monthly report on progress made and share it with TUD, according to the agreed template. In addition, the teachers may be called upon to make a brief presentation on the

implementation of the risk evaluation approach, in the upcoming project meetings in Solotvyno.

4. The Planned Outcomes

The outcomes of this assignment will be three-fold:

- Contribution to the ImProDiReT project deliverable 3.3: Risk evaluation approach through the collection of household survey data on the approved risk evaluation approach;
- The collected data will contribute to the development of a scientific paper on community-centered risk evaluation approaches, with the exact topic to be defined after data is collected; and
- Reporting and dissemination.

4. Assessment

The work of the teachers will be evaluated based on:

- The number and quality of filled in questionnaires;
- The quality and content of the monthly reports; and
- An oral presentation, when requested to do so.

5. Qualifications

1. Working knowledge of English.
2. Working knowledge of respective local languages spoken in their schools (Romanian, Ukrainian, Hungarian, Roma, Russian, Slovak and Czech).

6. Benefits

1. Working in / with the HumTechLab, closely working with experienced/leading researchers in the fields of humanitarian information management, logistics and disaster risk reduction.
2. Gain experience in an international EU project, working closely with project partners from the Ukraine, Netherlands, Poland.

7. Project setup

7.1 Resources and Finance

The teachers will receive a flat fee for Monthly Translation and Progress Report Writing Services of 400 Euros per month (32 hours per month), after submission of individual monthly invoices and receipts of payment. This is to facilitate the household data collection process and support students and other teachers.

7.2 Structure, Communication & Collaboration

The four teachers will form a team that will be coordinated by Viktoria Andyush. Viktoria Andyush will report to Abby Muricho Onencan. A group will be formed in Viber to facilitate the group communications.

7.3 Schedule & time commitment

Date Range	Activity	Responsible
July 1 st September 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Finalize TOR ▪ Complete draft questionnaire ▪ Get feedback from TUD, ImProDiReT team and the team of four Solotvyno teachers ▪ Finalize the questionnaires ▪ Develop a data management plan ▪ Get the questionnaire and the data management plan approved by the TUD privacy team 	Abby Muricho Onencan
1 st September to 7 th September	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Translate the questionnaire into Ukrainian, Hungarian and Romanian ▪ Prepare the teachers and students for the household survey and communicate any important information 	Solotvyno Teachers
7 th to 20 th September	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Print and disseminate the questionnaire to the four teachers 	Abby Muricho Onencan
20 th September	Meeting with teachers to clarify roles and prepare for the data collection exercise in Solotvyno	Abby Muricho Onencan
23 rd September	Initiation of the data collection	Solotvyno Teachers
5 th October 2019	Submit brief monthly reflection report for September 2019	Solotvyno Teachers
5 th October 2019	Submit brief monthly reflection report for October 2019	Solotvyno Teachers
5 th October 2019	Submit brief monthly reflection report for November 2019	Solotvyno Teachers
TBD	November meeting with the teachers in Solotvyno after the November project meeting	Abby Muricho

to complete the exercise and conduct a debriefing session

Onencan

8. Cost estimate

Month	Description of task	Teacher / School	Amount (32 hours @ 50 Euros per day / 8 hours)
September	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaire Monthly Translation and Progress Report Writing Services from English to the respective local languages used in the various schools. Training on use of the questionnaire to teachers and students (in local language). Agree with student specific neighbors who will fill the questionnaire (in local language). Discussion of household survey to the students, other teachers, parents and the neighbors identified to fill the questionnaire (in local language). Explanation of the consent form in local language (in local language) Monthly progress report (in English). 	Tsipile Olga / Romanian Secondary School of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Tyagunova Natalia / Ukrainian Secondary School of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Viktoria Andyush / Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Popp Adriana / Romanian Lyceum of Solotvyno	400 Euros
October	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued discussion and monitoring of household survey with the students, other teachers, parents and the neighbors identified to fill the questionnaire (in local language). Continued explanation of the consent form in local language (in local language) Monthly progress report (in English). 	Tsipile Olga / Romanian Secondary School of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Tyagunova Natalia / Ukrainian Secondary School of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Viktoria Andyush / Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Popp Adriana / Romanian Lyceum of Solotvyno	400 Euros
October	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final discussions and monitoring of household survey with the students, other teachers, parents and the neighbors identified to fill the questionnaire (in local language). Final explanations of the consent form in local language (in local language) Final progress report (in English). 	Tsipile Olga / Romanian Secondary School of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Tyagunova Natalia / Ukrainian Secondary School of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Viktoria Andyush / Hungarian Secondary School named after Yanosh Bolyay of Solotvyno	400 Euros
		Popp Adriana / Romanian Lyceum of Solotvyno	400 Euros
TOTAL			4,800 Euros

NB: Payment will be made directly to the identified teachers.

9. Monthly Outputs

The payment of the Monthly Translation and Progress Report Writing Service Fee will be based on submission of the following verifiable outputs:

Month	Output
September 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Translated questionnaire in local language ▪ 20% of teacher’s questionnaires filled ▪ All children ages 11-17 have filled the household survey questionnaire and consent form with their families ▪ Monthly report
October 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 30% of teacher’s questionnaires filled ▪ All children ages 11-17 have filled the household survey questionnaire and consent form with the first neighbor ▪ Monthly report
November 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 30% of teacher’s questionnaires filled ▪ All children ages 11-17 have filled the household survey questionnaire and consent form with the second neighbor ▪ Final report

10. Dissemination, acknowledgement & Attribution

The collected questionnaires will be delivered to TUD and the information kept confidential. The teachers’ contributions will be recognized in the final deliverable and any scientific publication. The data will be cleaned and all personal data removed. The final data which is safe to share will be uploaded in the 4TU website after the scientific publications are finalized.

1. Renn, O., *White paper on risk governance: Toward an integrative framework*, in *Global risk governance*. 2008, Springer. p. 3-73.
2. UNISDR, U.N.O. *Sendai framework for disaster risk reduction 2015–2030*. 2015. UNISDR Sendai, Japan.

Annex F: Soltvyno Municipality Data Management Plan (DMP)

Improving Disaster Risk Reduction in Transcarpathia, Ukraine (ImProDiReT)

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Creator: Abby Onencan

Affiliation: Delft University of Technology

Template: European Research Council (ERC)

ORCID iD: 0000-0002-5465-4806

Grant number: 783232

Project abstract:

ImProDiReT is a 2-year project funded (75%) by the Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (DG ECHO). The purpose of the overall research project is to develop a coordinated community-driven Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) action plan aimed at protecting and building the resilience of the Transcarpathian people, their environment, property and cultural heritage. The project objective is to develop new approaches and methods for the joint development of Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) strategies involving multiple stakeholders. These participatory approaches will be developed around specific case studies in the Transcarpathian region, in western Ukraine. The ImProDiReT project team consists of: the Resilience Advisors Network (RAN), the Regional Development Agency of Zakarpattia (ARDZ), the Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), the Institute of Geological Sciences of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (IGS-NASU) and the Main School of Fire Services (MSFS). The project is led by a steering group with representatives from the five institutions. This Data Management Plan has been developed for one of the project components: developing a risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno municipality, and performed by TU Delft. A household survey questionnaire has been developed to collect data from the inhabitants of Solotvyno municipality. The household survey data will be analyzed for the purpose of evaluating the level of acceptance, tolerability or intolerability to the land subsidence risk in the Solotvyno municipality. The household survey will thus produce several data sets: the risk evaluation sub-scale dataset, the disaster risk preparedness subscale dataset and the place attachment dataset. In addition, geo-referenced data will be collected to map the community perceptions on the land subsidence risk. After the data is collected, a text-based format (or zipped version thereof) will be used, which is appropriate, given that reproducibility is one of the project purposes. At the time of publication, the cleaned-up data will not include the Geo points, any personally identifiable information and all personal data. The cleaned-up data will be made available on the 4TU website, with a DOI for the data used to generate the results in the paper. Manuscripts will be prepared in Microsoft Word (.docx), with figures in standard formats (.pdf, .png, .jpg).

Last modified: 06-08-2019

Improving Disaster Risk Reduction in Transcarpathia, Ukraine (ImProDiReT)

Summary

Project Acronym

ImProDiReT

Project Number

783232

Provide a dataset summary

Purpose of the data collection	This project involves collecting information through a survey in Ukraine . TU Delft is the principal investigator of this project, and the project is funded by the European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operation (https://ec.europa.eu/echo/) The current goal is to start running the survey in September 2019. There is no data yet available on this topic, therefore new data need to be collected to address the project's questions and improve disaster risk governance in Solotvyno municipality. The aims of this research are to evaluate the level of acceptance, tolerability or intolerability to the land subsidence risk. Implementation of the risk evaluation questionnaire in this study will provide the necessary information to address the research question.
Relation to the objectives of the project	The database name is Solotvyno Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) Household Survey. It consists of quantitative survey data. The purpose of the survey is to evaluate the land subsidence risk, assess the preparedness of the Solotvyno community, the levels of acceptability or tolerability of the community to the risk and the attachment of the community to the place (Solotvyno municipality). Data will be collected through quantitative surveys collected by students and teachers from the four main schools in Solotvyno. The number of participants is expected to be in the range of 1000 (2000max).
Types and formats of data	Data collected Data collected includes Geo-Referenced data (points and polygons). Data format: Survey data: .csv format or related text-based format. Supplemented by pictures (photos)
Will existing data be re-used	No, there is no data yet available addressing this issue
The origin of the data	Data will be collected through quantitative surveys. The dataset is composed of several sub-dataset, each focused on a specific aspect of the study (land subsidence risk, risk preparedness, place attachment).
The expected size of the data	Less than 5GB
Data utility	The expected size of the data is less than 5GB. Research data resulting from this research will be of interested to the Solotvyno community, the project team, other researchers, the European Union, as well as Ukrainian policymakers.

FAIR data and resources

1. Making data findable

All non-personal data resulting from the project will be made openly available through the [4TU.Centre for Research Data](#). [4TU.Centre for Research Data](#) is a trusted and certified research data repository (it has a Data Seal of Approval certification).

The dataset will be accompanied by rich metadata (adhering to DataCite metadata standard) to ensure that all datasets are findable. In addition, to further aid their discoverability, keywords describing the dataset will be added.

4TU.Center for Research is also using [schema.org](#) metadata, meaning that all datasets are indexed in Google Dataset Search. Every dataset will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), to make them citable and persistently available. In addition, we will adhere to the [Data Documentation Initiative](#) standard for disciplinary-specific, rich description of all the data files created.

The data file will be named using the following elements in the file name:

- Date: YYYYMMDD
- Descriptive file name

- Initials of the person who last modified the file

In order to ensure that sensitive data is appropriately stored, from the start, all datasets will be stored in a dedicated encrypted project drive, provided and managed by TU Delft.

2. Making data openly accessible

All personal/sensitive data will be removed, at the end of the experiment, and we will keep the bare minimum, to prove that we have contacted real people. The anonymised data (surveys) will be retained for at least ten years on [4TU Centre for Research Data](#).

3. Making data interoperable

In order to facilitate data interoperability to the highest possible extent, we will:

- Create a dictionary of all terms used in our datasets. This dictionary will be publicly shared together with all the datasets at the end of the project.
- All datasets and metadata will be published in [4TU.Center for Research Data](#). 4TU.Center for Research Data uses Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) as the standard for metadata. Dublin Core is used worldwide. As a result, it is easy to link metadata to other files and automatically search through them, which increases the interoperability of the data.
- All documentation included in the datasets is provided as a README file in plain text format (.txt)

4. Increase data reuse

The data will be licensed under a CC-BY NC licence which requires attribution/credit for the original creation, while at the same time ensures broadest possible reuse for non-commercial purposes. Datasets will be made publicly available at the time of the publication of corresponding research papers resulting from this study. [4TU.Center for Research Data](#) (where the dataset will be deposited) ensures data quality and curation (manual curation at the time of deposition, and automated curation and checks for data integrity after the deposit). Research data will be available for at least 10 years from the time of data deposition. Personal / sensitive data is not going to be reused.

5. Allocation of resources and data security

Allocation of resources

[4TU.Center for Research Data](#) is able to archive 1TB of data per researcher per year free of charge for all TU Delft researchers. We do not expect to exceed this and therefore there are no additional costs of long term preservation.

The principal investigator (lead researcher) is responsible for data management in the project.

Data security

In the context of this research, information on household religious background and nationality, as well as localisation, are part of the raw data. It is expected that their answers will vary based on those criteria. To ensure that this special category of data is well managed, we have undertaken or plan to undertake the following data security measures:

- *Encryption solution.* VeraCrypt will be used to create an encrypted virtual drive (stored on the network project drive).
- *Handling Personal Data:* Any personal sensitive data, such as names, identities, will be replaced, scrambled or blurred to ensure that anonymized data cannot be linked back to the participant (e.g., in the questionnaire age will be approximated to a ten-year category). The anonymized data may be used for research and publications.
- *Ethics Screening:* The TUD project team plans to submit an application to the Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) meeting for August 2019, to ensure that the research is screened because it involves human subjects and ensures that implementation starts after approval.
- *Survey tool:* We are currently evaluating the compliance of various tools with privacy regulation (GDPR) to run the survey. Currently, Survey123, Kobotoolbox and Qualtrics are being considered. The survey will run either through paper-based documents or online. Currently, the online version is preferred and respondents will be encouraged to use the online version and only select to use the paper-based documents if the need arises.
- *Data storage during the study:* The survey tool storage has been checked and approved for privacy by the TBM Data Steward. In addition, a dedicated project drive, backed up and protected by TU Delft IT Services has been created. For the project duration (September 1 2019 - February 29, 2020), the sensitive and anonymized data will be stored in a dedicated project drive created by the Delft University of Technology that is encrypted, backed-up and protected by the Delft University of Technology IT Services. While the anonymized data will be available to other researchers with organizational login access (within the ImProDiReT project), the sensitive data will be stored in a separate folder with the additional unique password access, **available only to the researcher and the PI**. The data are stored in the Netherlands and are never made available to third parties.
- *Storage after the study:* After the project, the anonymized data and research results will be transferred to the 4TU.Center for Research Data as a secure data repository for a period of 10 years. The anonymized data will have open access – i.e. will be accessible to anyone. This repository complies with the international Data Seal of Approval standard. The data will be stored in the 4TU, license: CC-BY-NC. Survey answers will be deleted. Consent forms will be stored on the project drive until deemed unnecessary.
- *Reduce Potential Misuse of Research:* There will be no changes made to the demographic data because it may support the development of tailored risk mitigation strategies and communication tools for different local governance groups, based on their perception(s) and motivation(s). However, the aggregated data will anonymize these groups (no longer talking about Christian Romanian, but Group A, ...), to avoid potential misuse of the research results by third parties.

Annex G: Soltvyno Municipality Household Survey Consent Form

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Solotvyno Municipality Disaster Risk Reduction Household Survey

Before agreeing to participate in the study, it is important that you read the following explanation (pages 1 and 2). You (a participant) will be given a copy of this informed consent form.

Title of research: Risk Evaluation Approach for the Solotvyno Municipality

This study is part of the larger European Union project “Improving Disaster Risk Reduction in the Transcarpathia Region”, Ukraine - ImProDiReT (Principal Investigator (henceforth “PI”): **Prof. Bartel Van de Walle**, EU DG ECHO project 783232 on Risk Governance). More information on this project can be found here: <http://www.improdirect.eu/>

Researcher: Dr. Abby Muricho Onencan (henceforth “Researcher”), Department of Multi-Actor Systems, Section Policy Analysis, Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management, Delft University of Technology, NL

Purpose of the research

The purpose of the survey is to assess how we can make the Solotvyno community safe. The data will provide input for the community action plan to reduce risks associated to the collapse of the land near the salt mines.

Confidentiality and data management

We will collect information about the risk evaluation, the disaster risk preparedness and the place attachment. In addition, geo-referenced data will be collected to map the community perceptions on the land subsidence risk.

Processing and storing of your data will be handled in accordance with the European Union 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation. You have the right to request access to, change or erasure of your personal data at any time.

- Any personal sensitive data, such as names, identities, location, will be replaced, scrambled or blurred to ensure that anonymized data cannot be linked back to you. The anonymized data may be used for research and publications.
- For the project duration (September 1 2019 - February 29, 2020), personal information will only be accessible to the project members (the Researcher and PI). The data are stored in the Netherlands and are never made available to third parties.
- After the project, the **anonymized data and research results (non-personal)** will be archived for a period of 10 years and will be accessible to anyone

Explanation of procedures

You will be invited to answer a set of questions about your perceptions of the land subsidence risk in Solotvyno municipality, your level of preparedness and how attached you are to the area. The estimated duration to answer the questions ranges from 15 - 30 minutes.

Risks

The main risks of participating in the study are linked to the interception of your personal data during the processing and storage of the information provided by you to complete this study. The researcher has minimized the risks by using only the anonymized data that cannot be linked back to you and taking the

appropriate measures of storage and access control to secure the sensitive data during and after the project. The data interception risks are thus minimal.

Participation in the survey is otherwise safe for the participants. By participating in this study, you do not undergo specific health risks.

Questions

Any questions concerning the research and the survey and/or in the case of issues due to the research can be directed to the researcher, Abby M. Onencan, TU Delft /Faculty of TPM, Jaffalaan 5, 2628 BX Delft, Email: A.M.Onencan@tudelft.nl.

After reading the explanation of the study above, please, answer the following questions by ticking the “Yes” or “No” boxes with “x” or “√”

Description	Yes	No
1. I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked were answered to my satisfaction.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. I voluntarily consent to be a participant in this study. I understand that I can refuse to answer questions and I can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. I understand that taking part in the study involves the risk of the interception of my personal data during the processing and storage of the information provided by me to complete this study. I furthermore understand that the researcher has minimized the risks by taking the appropriate measures of storage and access control to secure the sensitive data during and after the project (see Page 1).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. I understand that the anonymized information (anonymized survey transcript) I provide will be used for publications and other research related activities (e.g., reports, website, blogs, etc.).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me, where I live, will not be shared beyond the researcher and the PI.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<p>Participant's name:</p> <p>Participant's signature:</p> <p>Place, date of signing:</p>

Annex H: HREC Application and Approval Letter

Delft University of Technology
ETHICS REVIEW CHECKLIST FOR HUMAN RESEARCH
(Version 01.02.2019)

This checklist should be completed for every research study that involves human participants and should be submitted before potential participants are approached to take part in your research study.

In this checklist we will ask for additional information if need be. Please attach this as an Annex to the application.

Please upload the documents (go to [this page](#) for instructions).

Thank you and please check our [website](#) for guidelines, forms, best practices, meeting dates of the HREC, etc.

I. Basic Data

Project title:	Improving Disaster Risk Reduction in the Transcarpathian Region, Ukraine (ImProDiReT)
Name(s) of researcher(s):	Dr. Abby Muricho Onencan ¹ Ir. Drs Kenny Meesters ²
Research period (planning)	September – November 2019
E-mail contact person	a.m.onencan@tudelft.nl
Faculty/Dept.	Technology, Policy and Management / Multi-Actor Systems (MAS)
Position researcher(s):¹	Post-doc ¹ PhD ²
Name of supervisor (if applicable):	Prof. Bartel Van de Walle
Role of supervisor (if applicable):	Approve and review the research

II. A) Summary Research

(Please very briefly (100-200 words) summarise your research, stating the question for the research, who will participate, the number of participants to be tested and the methods/devices to be used. Please avoid jargon and abbreviations).

This study is part of the larger European Union ImProDiReT project. More information on this project can be found here: <http://www.improdiret.eu/>. The principal Investigator (henceforth "PI") is Prof. Bartel Van de Walle.

The purpose of the survey is to evaluate the level of acceptance, tolerability or intolerability to the land subsidence risk in the Solotvyno municipality. The survey will be conducted through the four major schools in Solotvyno and coordinated by the English-speaking teachers. Other teachers and students will support the household survey data collection process in their respective homes and neighbourhoods. The number of participants is in the range of 1000 (2000max). The current goal is to start running the survey in September this year.

Only quantitative and localisation data will be collected using an online survey tool. In addition, a consent form, will be completed. These two documents will be translated into locally spoken languages (mainly Ukrainian, Hungarian and Romanian).

¹ For example: student, PhD, post-doc

B) Risk assessment

Please indicate if you expect any potential risks for the participants as a result of your research and, if so, how you will try to minimize these.

In the context of this research, information on household religious background and nationality, as well as localisation, are a part of the raw data. It is expected that their answers will vary based on those criteria. To ensure that this special category of data is well managed, processing and storing of your data will be handled in accordance with the European Union 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation, as outlined in the data management plan.

III. Checklist

Question	Yes	No
1. Does the study involve participants who are particularly vulnerable or unable to give informed consent? (e.g., children, people with learning difficulties, patients, people receiving counselling, people living in care or nursing homes, people recruited through self-help groups).		X
2. Are the participants, outside the context of the research, in a dependent or subordinate position to the investigator (such as own children or own students)? ²		X
3. Will it be necessary for participants to take part in the study without their knowledge and consent at the time? (e.g., covert observation of people in non-public places).		X
4. Will the study involve actively deceiving the participants? (For example, will participants be deliberately falsely informed, will information be withheld from them or will they be misled in such a way that they are likely to object or show unease when debriefed about the study).		X
5. Personal data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Will the study involve discussion or collection of confidential (sensitive) personal data? (e.g., BSN number, location, sexual activity, drug use, mental health)? 	X	
If 'yes': Did the data steward approve your data management plan? Please upload proof.	X	
6. Will drugs, placebos, or other substances (e.g., drinks, foods, food or drink constituents, dietary supplements) be administered to the study participants?		X
7. Will blood or tissue samples be obtained from participants?		X
8. Is pain or more than mild discomfort likely to result from the study?		X
9. Does the study risk causing psychological stress or anxiety or other harm or negative consequences beyond that normally encountered by the participants in their life outside research?		X

² **Important note concerning questions 1 and 2.** Some intended studies involve research subjects who are particularly vulnerable or unable to give informed consent. Research involving participants who are in a dependent or unequal relationship with the researcher or research supervisor (e.g., the researcher's or research supervisor's students or staff) may also be regarded as a vulnerable group. If your study involves such participants, it is essential that you safeguard against possible adverse consequences of this situation (e.g., allowing a student's failure to complete their participation to your satisfaction to affect your evaluation of their coursework). This can be achieved by ensuring that participants remain anonymous to the individuals concerned (e.g., you do not seek names of students taking part in your study). If such safeguards are in place, or the research does not involve other potentially vulnerable groups or individuals unable to give informed consent, it is appropriate to check the NO box for questions 1 and 2. Please describe corresponding safeguards in the summary field.

Question	Yes	No
10. Will financial inducement (other than reasonable expenses and compensation for time) be offered to participants?		X
Important: if you answered 'yes' to any of the questions mentioned above, please submit a full application to HREC (see: website for forms or examples).		
11. Will the experiment collect and store videos, pictures, or other identifiable data of human subjects? ³ <i>If "yes", please fill in Annex 1 and make you sure you follow all requirements of the applicable data protection legislation. In addition, please provide proof by sending us a copy of the informed consent form.</i>		X
12. Will the experiment involve the use of devices that are not 'CE' certified? <i>Only, if 'yes': continue with the following questions:</i>		X
➤ Was the device built in-house?		
➤ Was it inspected by a safety expert at TU Delft? <i>(Please provide device report, see: HREC website)</i>		
➤ If it was not built in house and not CE-certified, was it inspected by some other, qualified authority in safety and approved? <i>(Please provide records of the inspection).</i>		
13. Has or will this research be submitted to a research ethics committee other than this one? <i>(if so, please provide details and a copy of the approval or submission).</i>		X

IV. Enclosures (tick if applicable)

- X Full proposal (if 'yes' to any of the questions 1 until 10)
- √ Informed consent form (if 'yes' to question 11)
- X Device report (if 'yes' to question 12)
- X Approval other HREC-committee (if 'yes' to question 13)
- X Any other information which might be relevant for decision making by HREC
- √ Link to [Data management plan approved by a data steward](#) (if yes to question 5B)

³ Note: you have to ensure that collected data is safeguarded physically and will not be accessible to anyone outside the study. Furthermore, the data has to be de-identified if possible and has to be destroyed after a scientifically appropriate period of time. Also ask explicitly for consent if anonymised data will be published as open data.

V. **Signature(s)**

Signature(s) of researcher(s)

Date	Name	Signature
6 th August 2019	Abby Muricho Onencan	

6th August 2019 Kenny Meesters

Research supervisor (if applicable)

Date	Name	Signature
12 August 2019	Bartel Van de Walle	

Appendix 1: Privacy and data protection

Please fill this in if you have answered 'yes' to question 11 in the checklist

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- Will the participants have access to their own data? If no, please explain.
 - Will covert methods be used? (*e.g. participants are filmed without them knowing*)
 - Will any human tissue and/or biological samples be collected? (*e.g. urine*)

Date 27-08-2019
Contact person Ir. J.B.J. Groot Kormelink, secretary HREC
Telephone +31 152783260
E-mail j.b.j.grootkormelink@tudelft.nl

Human Research Ethics Committee
TU Delft
(<http://hrec.tudelft.nl/>)

Visiting address
Jaffalaan 5 (building 31)
2628 BX Delft

Postal address
P.O. Box 5015 2600 GA Delft
The Netherlands

Ethics Approval Application: Solotvyno Municipality Disaster Risk Reduction Household Survey
Applicant: Onencan, Abby

Dear Abby Onencan,

It is a pleasure to inform you that your application mentioned above has been approved.

Good luck with your research!

Sincerely,

Dr. Ir. W.P. Brinkman
Vice chair HREC
Faculty EEMCS

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